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Freiberg, 26 April 2022

.....

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Summary

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) are advanced engineered materials that have gained great attention in the past decade. The composites made by light, stiff ceramic particles enhance their properties and make them lightweight. The high-modulus steel (HMS) Fe-TiB₂ is an MMC, which shows similar attributes to the lightweight material. The HMS can be processed by conventional casting, spray forming, and additive manufacturing. Fe-TiB₂ processed by conventional casting demonstrates bad mechanical properties due to the precipitation of larger TiB₂ particles in the Fe-matrix. Slow solidification kinetics of the conventional casting process coarsens the precipitated particles and deteriorates mechanical performance. Rapid solidification (cooling rate $\sim 10^4 - 10^6$ K/s) process can overcome this challenge. The spray forming process is a rapid solidification process where nano-structured precipitates are formed. The laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) process showed similar-sized precipitation due to its the rapid solidification characteristic.

In this work, the in-situ processing of Fe-TiB₂ MMC from powder-mixture via L-PBF is investigated. A hypothesis is proposed that the Fe-TiB₂ MMC can be processed using a mixture of elementary and binary alloy powders. The metal powder used in for the L-PBF process are produced by a close-coupled gas atomizer. Atomized powders' size distribution, morphology are investigated and their flowability is measured to derive processibility in the L-PBF process. Different process parameters for the L-PBF process are studied and selected. The samples are produced by the L-PBF process at room temperature (single laser scan) and remelting strategy with substrate preheating (400 °C). The types and amount of defect are quantified. Furthermore, the microstructures of different samples are investigated by using SEM, EDX and XRD analysis methods.

The printed samples at room temperature show a higher fraction of defects and larger cracks are formed at the bottom and side edges of the samples and propagates throughout the samples. However, remelting strategy with substrate preheating show an improvement in the samples by reducing porosities and by eliminating the cracks from the samples. Remelting strategy reduces the fraction of defects from eight percent to around two percent. SEM images show the formation of nano-structured dark particles in the powder-mixture samples similar to the pre-alloyed samples. The obtained result supports the proposed hypothesis that, in-situ Fe-TiB₂ MMC processing is possible by powder-mixture via L-PBF process. EDX images show the concentration of Ti and B in the grain boundaries. However,

XRD analysis show hardly any peaks for TiB_2 for the pre-alloyed and powder-mixture samples processed at room temperature.

Zusammenfassung

Metallmatrix-Verbundwerkstoffe (MMC) sind hochentwickelte technische Werkstoffe, die in den letzten zehn Jahren große Beachtung gefunden haben. Die Verbundwerkstoffe werden aus leichten, steifen Keramikpartikeln hergestellt, welche die Eigenschaften verbessern und sie leicht machen. Der Hochmodulstahl (HMS) Fe-TiB₂ ist ein MMC, welcher ähnliche Eigenschaften aufweist. Der HMS kann durch konventionelles Gießen, Spritzgießen und additive Fertigung verarbeitet werden. Fe-TiB₂, das durch konventionelles Gießen verarbeitet wird, weist aufgrund größerer TiB₂-Partikel in der Fe-Matrix schlechte mechanische Eigenschaften auf. Die langsame Erstarrungskinetik des konventionellen Gießverfahrens vergrößert die ausgefällten Partikel und verschlechtert die mechanischen Eigenschaften. Eine schnelle Erstarrung (Abkühlungsrate $\sim 10^4 - 10^6$ K/s) kann dieses Problem überwinden. Das Sprühformverfahren ist ein schneller Erstarrungsprozess, bei dem nanostrukturierte Ausscheidungen gebildet werden. Das Laser-Pulver-Bett-Fusionsverfahren (L-PBF) zeigt aufgrund seiner schnellen Erstarrungscharakteristik ähnlich große Ausscheidungen.

In dieser Arbeit wird die In-situ-Verarbeitung von Fe-TiB₂ MMC aus einer Pulvermischung mittels L-PBF untersucht. Es wird die Hypothese aufgestellt, dass Fe-TiB₂ MMC mit einer Mischung aus elementaren und binären Legierungspulvern verarbeitet werden kann. Die Metallpulver, die für das L-PBF-Verfahren verwendet werden, werden mit einem Close-Coupled-Gaszerstäuber erzeugt. Die Größenverteilung und Morphologie der zerstäubten Pulver werden untersucht und ihre Fließfähigkeit gemessen, um die Verarbeitbarkeit im L-PBF-Verfahren abzuleiten. Es werden verschiedene Prozessparameter für das L-PBF-Verfahren untersucht und ausgewählt. Die Proben werden mit dem L-PBF-Verfahren mittels Einzellaserscan bei Raumtemperatur und Doppellaserscan (Remeltingstrategie) mit Substratvorwärmung (400 °C) hergestellt. Die Art und Menge der Defekte wird quantifiziert. Außerdem wird die Mikrostruktur mit Hilfe von REM-, EDX- und XRD-Analysemethoden untersucht.

Die gedruckten Proben bei Raumtemperatur weisen einen höheren Anteil an Defekten auf und größere Risse bilden sich an den unteren und seitlichen Kanten und breiten sich in den Proben aus. Die Remeltingstrategie mit Substratvorwärmung führt jedoch zu einer Verbesserung der Proben, indem die Porosität verringert und die Risse behoben werden. Die Umschmelzstrategie reduziert den Anteil der Defekte von acht Prozent auf etwa zwei Prozent. REM-Bilder zeigen die Bildung von dunklen Partikeln mit Nanostruktur in den

Proben mit Pulvermischung, die den vorlegierten Proben ähneln. Die erzielten Ergebnisse unterstützen die vorgeschlagene Hypothese, dass die Herstellung von Fe-TiB₂-MMC in-situ durch Pulvermischung mittels L-PBF-Prozess möglich ist. EDX-Bilder zeigen die Konzentration von Ti und B an den Korngrenzen. Die XRD-Analyse zeigt jedoch kaum Peaks für TiB₂ für die vorlegierten und die bei Raumtemperatur verarbeiteten Pulvermischungsproben.

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Symbols and Abbreviations

Symbol	Description	Unit
Roman Letters		
\dot{Q}_p	Heat energy	J/s
AR_{50}	Mean aspect ratio	m
B_R	Building rate	m ³ /s
c_p	Specific heat capacity	J/kgK
d_L	Spot diameter	m
d_{50}	Mass median particle diameter	m
d	Spot diameter	m
E	Modulus of elasticity	Gpa
E_V	Volume energy density	J/m ³
$E_{v,1}$	1 st laser scan energy density	J/m ³
$E_{v,2}$	2 nd laser scan energy density	J/m ³
E'_V	Effective volume energy density	J/m ³
E_{total}	Total energy density	m ³ /s
H	Height	m
H_R	Hausner ratio	-
h	Hatch distance	m
m	Mass	kg
P_L	Laser power	W
p_G	Atomization gas pressure	MPa
Q3	Cumulative mass distribution (volume-based)	-

q_3	Distribution density (volume-based)	1/ μm
R	Radius	m
T_L	Liquidus temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
T_p	Powder temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
T_s	Substrate temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
t	Layer thickness	m
v_s	Scanning velocity	m/s
v_t	Transport velocity	m/s
v_d	Deposition velocity	m/s

Symbol	Description	Unit
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Greek Letters

α_p	Dynamic angle of repose	$^{\circ}$
ρ	Density	kg/m^3
ρ_t	Tapped density	kg/m^3
ρ_b	Bulk density	kg/m^3
λ	Wavelength	m
ΔT	Temperature difference	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Δt	Temperature difference	s
ΔH	Change of enthalpy	J/kgK
θ	Contact angle	$^{\circ}$
φ	Specific modulus	$\text{Gpa} \cdot \text{m}^3/\text{kg}$
\varnothing_n	Pouring nozzle diameter	m

Symbol	Description	Unit
Abbreviations		
AM	Additive manufacturing	-
BF	Bright field	-
CAD	Computer-aided design	-
CCA	Close-coupled atomizer	-
CLI	Common layer interface	-
DF	Dark field	-
DIC	Differential interference contrast	-
EDM	Electrical discharge machining	-
EDX	Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy	-
FFA	Free-fall atomizer	-
GMR	Gas-to-melt flow rate	-
HMS	High-modulus steel	-
L-PBF	Laser powder bed fusion	-
MMC	Metal matrix composites	-
PM	Powder-mixture	-
PSD	Particle size distribution	-
ROI	Region of interest	-
RT	Room temperature	-
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy	-
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy	-
VED	Volume energy density	-
XRD	X-ray diffraction	-

1 Introduction

We live in an era where science and technology are achieved the peak of the invention. Therefore, engineers and scientists are putting a lot more emphasis on improvisation. Metal matrix composites (MMC) have become an inevitable part of material science and engineering. Ceramic reinforced MMC is one of the prominent materials for its excellent lightweight properties. It significantly improves machine energy consumption and performance by reducing weight. It also exhibits very good mechanical properties such as hardness, tensile strength, corrosion resistivity, etc. MMCs' have attracted researchers' interest over the past decades. Researchers are trying to improve their properties to make them more suitable for complex applications in different fields such as automotive, aerospace, energy etc. [1].

High-modulus steel (HMS) addresses all the key criteria of light weight material [2]. HMS offers very good mechanical properties such as tensile density, hardness by creating composite microstructures. The composite microstructures can be achieved by blending light and stiff particles into strong and ductile metal matrices [3]. Different process routes can be followed for processing of HMS such as conventional casting, spray forming, and additive manufacturing. HMS processed by conventional casting exhibits coarser particles as precipitates (TiB_2) in the Fe- matrix which can not undergo heavy load and cracks form easily. The particles are coarsening in conventional casting due to the slow solidification kinetics [4]. Solidification is an important factor for processing any material. The term solidification means solid-state formation of a material with or without a chemical reaction from the gaseous or liquid parent materials. This is classified as slow and rapid solidification. Rapid solidification (e.g. $10^4 - 10^6$ K/s) needs a very short time to convert into a solid phase from liquid or gaseous phase [5]. Spray forming is a rapid solidification process [6]. Spray forming technology shows prominent microstructure refinement by forming nano-structure TiB_2 because of the rapid solidification process [7]. This refined microstructure showed elevated mechanical properties by increasing the stiffness of the material. Laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) process is also a rapid solidification process. The L-PBF process has been used to process HMS [4]. Through L-PBF, it is possible to produce nano-structured TiB_2 in Fe-matrix from pre-alloyed powders by rapid solidification.

Additive manufacturing techniques is a new opportunity to produce HMS. The L-PBF process is an additive manufacturing system that has many degrees of freedom [8]. Laser based additive manufacturing has mainly four advantages:

- It can produce complex shaped components which are difficult to produce by other manufacturing processes such as casting or machining.
- It is a very fast, direct process and easy to control.
- It reduces the waste material and reduces the yield losses in the manufacturing process.
- An immense extent of reusability and recycling by this process is possible.

L-PBF becomes highly suitable for the production of functional parts in small or even mid-scale series. Important fields such as aviation and energy industry are using L-PBF technology [9]. Up to now Fe-TiB₂ has been processed from pre-alloyed powders via L-PBF process. There is hardly any work found, which focuses on powder mixing approach to produced in-situ Fe-TiB₂. The aim of this work is to investigate Fe-TiB₂ HMS processing via powder mixing. Different approaches like variation of powder-mixtures and L-PBF process parameters will be introduced to produce defectless materials with high relative density.

2 State of the Art

The main purpose of this chapter is to discuss metal matrix composite (MMC), laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) process, different process parameters of the L-PBF, metallurgical characteristics of the printed materials, and powder production using gas atomization technology. Previous and current works in the research field of the additive manufacturing (AM) will be reviewed also. It will provide better understanding about the current state of the art and the area which needs further investigation.

2.1 Metal matrix composite

A pair or more components are used to make a composite material. Metal matrix composites (MMC) are also a combination of two or more components, from which one must be a metal compound and another will be reinforcement, such as intermetallic compounds or ceramic particles [10]. MMCs are very useful in many areas of our daily life, specially when we think about the lightweight materials [11]. MMCs combine metallic properties (e.g. ductility and toughness) with ceramic characteristics (e.g. high strength and modulus), leading to greater strength in shear and compression [12]. It provides higher service temperature capabilities. MMCs have important physical and mechanical properties such as high specific modulus, strength, and thermal stability when compared to traditional materials [13]–[15].

Different kinds of metal matrixes are developed, such as iron, aluminum, titanium, magnesium-based and so on [16]. Among them, iron is one of the most suitable metal compounds as a metal matrix. Iron exhibits a better specific modulus (stiffness to weight ratio) as all other widely used metals. Iron is widely available, is used in various fields, and has a great demand in the industry. Moreover, it demonstrates great mechanical properties such as tensile strength, hardness, toughness etc. The value of the Young modulus of iron is 190 to 210 GPa. However, for iron, the effects of alloying elements and microstructure are limited. To increase the stiffness and decrease the density, it has to be mixed with different compounds that allow increasing specific modulus [2].

The specific module φ is defined by the following equation,

$$\varphi = \frac{E}{\rho} \left[\text{Gpa} * \frac{\text{cm}^3}{\text{g}} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

Where, E = modulus of elasticity [GPa], and ρ = density [$\frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}$]. MMCs are materials made up of stiff ceramic reinforcements embedded in a ductile metal or alloy matrix. Presence of ceramics in metal matrix can lower the density and increased Young's modulus [17]. Ceramic reinforced iron and steel matrix composites show isotropic characteristics and have received extensive attention for research in recent years [18]. There are many potential reinforcing elements for the metal matrix composites, such as carbides, nitrides, borides, and several oxide materials [19]. The reinforcing elements (Figure 2.1) present in the matrix are in the form of particles, fibers or monofilaments [20]–[22].

Figure 2.1 Types of MMC a) continuous fibers b) whiskers short fibers c) particles [22].

Detailed properties of different reinforcing elements are shown in Table 2-1. An improved material's properties can result in the extension of the application area or the substitution of conventional materials [11]. TiB_2 is considered the promising reinforcement elements among the other due to its great mechanical performance such as high specific modulus of $120 \text{ Gpa} * \text{m}^3/\text{kg}$, and low density [23]. Moreover, TiB_2 is chemically stable as a secondary phase in the liquid iron [24]. Fe- TiB_2 is the most commonly researched HMS alloy system.

Zhang et al. demonstrated the phase diagram of the pseudo-binary Fe-TiB₂ system [24]. Lower density of the TiB₂ particle compared to other metals increases the stiffness of the material and makes it lightweight, which is shown in Figure 2.2 [2]. In addition, the steel metal matrix with reinforced TiB₂ offers higher hardness and wear resistance capability [25].

Table 2-1 Properties of various particles for reinforcement of metals [11].

Type of Particle	TiB ₂	SiC	Al ₂ O ₃	AlN	BN	TiC
Type of crystal	hex.	hex.	hex.	hex.	hex.	cub.
Melting Temperature [°C]	2900	2300	2050	2300	3000	3140
Young's modulus [GPa]	370	480	410	350	90	320
Density [g cm ⁻³]	4.5	3.21	3.9	3.25	2.25	4.93
Heat conductivity [Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	27	59	25	10	25	29
Thermal Coefficient of expansion [10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹]	7.4	4.7-5.0	8.3	6.0	3.8	7.4

Figure 2.2 Reinforcement selection criteria: The specific modulus E/ρ of most particle phases is higher [2].

2.1.1 High-modulus steel (HMS)

High modulus steel (HMS) offers superior performance where energy consumption is needed to reduce [2]. Fe-TiB₂ based HMS is depends on the ceramic constituent. Different volume fraction of TiB₂ demonstrates different mechanical properties. Figure 2.3 shows the effects of TiB₂ particle fraction on HMS [23]. Higher TiB₂ fraction improves the HMS mechanical performance by increasing specific modulus.

Figure 2.3 Change of specific modulus of HMS with addition of TiB₂ content [23]. Increasing vol.% of TiB₂ improves the performance.

2.1.2 Processing of HMS

Three different processing routes are usually used to produce Fe-TiB₂ HMS, which are:

- i) Conventional casting
- ii) Spray forming
- iii) Additive manufacturing

Processing by the conventional casting process is associated with slow solidification kinetics, which results in relatively coarse and sharp-edged particles. By spray forming technology, it is possible to get nano sized TiB₂ particles due to its rapid solidification kinetics (Figure 2.4). Springer et al. reported similar nano sized dispersion of the TiB₂

particles in Fe-matrix using L-PBF technology [4]. However, processing by L-PBF process is hardly investigated in depth up to now.

Figure 2.4 Microstructure characterization result by SEM after a) conventional casting b) spray forming c) L-PBF technology. Nano structured particles and matrix through spray forming and AM is evident [3], [4].

2.2 Additive manufacturing process

Additive manufacturing (AM) is a 3D printing process that involves the technology of building a part layer by layer. The stereolithography technique was the first patent on AM in 1986 [26]. According to the international standard ISO/ASTM 52900, the definition of AM is "process of joining materials to produce parts from 3D model data, usually layer upon layer" [27]. AM technique is convenient and faster than the traditional casting process. It reduces the machining process of the material after manufacturing and can be used to create a complex shaped material [28]. The computer-aided design (CAD) software first generates the model which is to be printed and then feeds it into the AM machine to print the end product. The routes of the AM techniques are shown in the Figure 2.5 [29]. AM is presently used in various fields of engineering, such as aerospace, automotive, medical, consumer goods, etc.

Additive manufacturing is classified based on the input energy-powder interaction and the consolidation mechanism [30]. Various types of AM methods are present now. Among them, selective laser melting (SLM), electron beam melting (EBM), selective laser sintering (SLS), and laser engineered net shaping (LENS) are the most frequently used techniques because they demonstrate great mechanical and thermal properties [31], [32]. Figure 2.6 demonstrates different AM methods used for metals, polymers, and ceramic materials. L-PBF process route has been considered in the present study [33].

Figure 2.5 Additive manufacturing process steps to produce any physical object [29].

Figure 2.6 Different types of additive manufacturing methods [33]. Considered process routes in this present study is shown in blue colors.

2.3 Laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF)

Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) is an additive manufacturing technology. It fuses the metal powder by using a high energy laser beam [33], [34]. The L-PBF process requires a number of steps, from computer-aided design (CAD) data preparation to the removal of construction material from the building platform [35]. CAD file converted to common layer interface (.CLI) format, which contains 3-dimensional information in the form of a triangular surface element. CLI format is completed by Autodesk software such as Netfabb® [36]. In this software, slicing is performed according to the layer thickness. The scanning strategy is also assigned by this software. Afterwards, this design imported to the Aconity 3D Mini machine for printing the sample [37]. The whole process is shown in Figure 2.7 illustrates the basic working principle of the L-PBF process [38].

During printing, the printing chamber is closed with proper sealing so that the external environment cannot affect the printing of the material. The printing chamber is kept neutral by purging inert gases such as Ar or N₂. This way, oxidation can be avoided [39]. Powder operation is divided into two parts: coater and feeder. Coater provides the powder for building each layer.

Figure 2.7 Process routes for the production of material by laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) [38].

The powder is lifted by a piston from a powder reservoir (supplier) and the coater pushes the powder over the substrate plate according to the predefined layer thickness. Then the high energy laser beam melts the powder by predefined printing strategy. After printing one layer, the substrate plate gets lowered and the powder reservoir goes up according to the predefined layer thickness [35]. To print subsequent layer, coater again pushes the powder

over the substrate plate and this process keeps repeating until the desired parts have been printed. Details of L-PBF machine are shown schematically in Figure 2.8 [40]. After finishing the printing, the printed part is separated from the substrate plate manually. The remaining powder is then collected from the printing chamber [41]. This powder can be reused after sieving. This process offers an ecological advantage.

Figure 2.8 Schematic of typical L-PBF machine shows different parts [40].

Substrate preheating is principally seen as an advantageous method in L-PBF [42]. It reduces the process induced thermal stresses and corresponding negative consequences like crack formation or distortion. The heat is distributed from the substrate plate into the part by thermal conduction. In Aconity 3D Mini, substrate plate can be preheated at different temperatures (up to 800 °C) [43].

2.3.1 Process parameters in L-PBF

L-PBF process parameters determine printed components' quality. The process parameter can be divided into four categories: (a) laser-related parameters (b) scan-related parameters (c) powder-related parameters (d) temperature-related parameters. All the independent parameters interact together to produce dense components' [44]. Among these, the most commonly studied parameters are:

- i) Laser power
- ii) Scanning velocity
- iii) Spot size
- iv) Hatch distance
- v) Powder layer thickness
- vi) Scanning strategy

Each process has advantages and disadvantages. To produce a high-density component, the above parameters must be taken into account in accordance with the material properties [45]–[47]. Figure 2.9 illustrates commonly studied process parameters for L-PBF [48].

Figure 2.9 Schematic illustration of most commonly used L-PBF process parameters [48].

High laser power results in parts with greater density [49]. However, it can create some inconvenience such as curling of the printed parts, have poor recyclability and difficult to clean. The Heat generated at high laser power at room temperature builds up residual stress [50]. Also, non-uniform expansion or shrinkage happens at high laser power. The downside of high laser power, it results in lower density parts with a higher tendency for layer delamination [51]. Bosio et al. reported that low laser power does not melt the powder enough, which results in inadequate adhesion between two layers [49], [52], [53].

The scanning velocity determined the building rate of the material. Shorter scanning velocity causes insufficient fusion of the powder. The longer the scanning velocity [54], the longer the laser dwells in a particular position to fuse metal powder [55]. This results in a larger fusion depth and melt pool diameter. Unoptimized scanning velocity can cause porosity. Thijs et al. reported that optimized scanning velocity can reduce the porosity of the final parts [55]. The diameter of the laser beam is referred to as the spot size. Laser beam exposures create a melt pool. Typically, a Gaussian laser spot is used in L-PBF [56]. The spacing between the center lines of two neighboring laser scanning tracks is known as the hatch distance [57]. A schematical illustration of spot diameter and hatch distance is shown in Figure 2.10 [54].

Figure 2.10 Schematical illustration showing (a) the pulsed laser melting process and the definition of key physical parameters such as (b) point distance and (c) hatch distance [54].

Layer thickness is the thickness of each layer considered in the building direction. In the L-PBF process, maximum productivity can be achieved with higher layer thickness. But it

consists of various process instabilities, yielding poor track quality and unrepeatability in geometrical features [58].

Different scanning strategies are available for the L-PBF process shown in Figure 2.11 [40]. A proper scanning strategy can yield in extremely dense components [59]. A distinct layer can be scanned using various scanning strategies. The bi-directional scanning strategy is the most standard strategy among the others. The island strategy is where the components are subdivided into smaller areas that distribute heat evenly over the layers [60]. The fractal scanning strategy creates layers of short scans with different orientations [61]. The helix scanning strategy starts scanning from the outside of the part and moves inwards or vice-versa. It is suitable for processing complex models where the curvature changes frequently or where the layers have irregularities and inconsistent thicknesses [62].

Figure 2.11 Schematical illustration of different scanning strategies (a) bi-directional (b) island (c) fractal (d) helix [40].

The energy required for melting the powder bed is called volume energy density (VED). It is the function of different laser parameter [55].

$$E_v = \frac{P_L}{v_s \times t \times h} \left[\frac{J}{mm^3} \right] \quad (2.2)$$

where, P_L = laser power [W], v_s = scanning velocity [mm/s], t = powder layer thickness [μ m], and h = Hatch distance [μ m]. The effective volume energy density E'_v can be approximately described by the spot diameter d of the laser [63].

$$E'_v = \frac{P_L}{\pi v_s \times d} \left[\frac{J}{mm^3} \right] \quad (2.3)$$

here, d = spot diameter [μm]. For industrial applications, the buildup rate B_R , which results from the selected process parameters, is also important to consider. It depends on the scanning velocity, hatch distance and layer thickness as [64]:

$$B_R = v_s \times t \times h \left[\frac{\text{mm}^3}{\text{s}} \right]. \quad (2.4)$$

2.3.2 Laser and metal powder interaction

The L-PBF process is designed to heat and melt of the metal powder by inducing laser power. Lasers are widely used for different material processing modalities [65]. Various types of lasers are present for different manufacturing processes, such as carbon dioxide laser, Nd: YAG (rod and disk) lasers, fiber laser, diode laser, and ultra-short Ti-sapphire/fiber lasers. When such laser comes into contact with the metal powders, a part of laser power is reflected, some part is absorbed in the material, and the remaining is transmitted [66]. The fractions of reflected, absorbed, and transmitted laser power depend primarily on the laser wavelength and the refractive index of the materials.

Different metals have different absorptivity rates. Absorptivity is the ratio of absorbed radiation to incident radiation. It is a function of both the material and the wavelength of the incident radiation [67]. The absorption of the energy flux irradiates onto the metal powder causes an increase in temperature. When this temperature reaches liquidus temperature, a melt pool is generated [48]. A basic laser and metal interaction is illustrated in Figure 2.12 [68].

Figure 2.12 Interaction between laser and metal powder to generate melt pool in L-PBF process [68].

2.3.3 Metallurgical characteristics

In the L-PBF process, unoptimized process parameters are responsible for various types of metallurgical characteristics such as balling, porosity, cracks, anisotropy, etc. Metallurgical characteristics determine the performance of the component. Metallurgical characteristics that have been studied before will be presented here.

2.3.3.1 Balling

The balling phenomenon occurs due to the selected process parameters where the powder cannot evenly spread on the previously printed layer [69]. A schematic diagram of balling is shown in Figure 2.13 [70]. During melting, partially molten metal creates a sphere-shaped ball. It has two disadvantages to the final product.

- i) Pore formation occurs inside the metal part, which deteriorates the mechanical properties and increases the surface roughness.
- ii) Due to this effect, the roller generates high friction during the spread of the powder on the previous layer. This damages the quality of the printed surface [71].

Figure 2.13 Schematic diagram of different types of balling formation during L-PBF process [70].

The wetting behavior between the solid surface and the molten pool determines the size of balling. The contact angle θ is the angle between the liquid and solid surface (see Figure 2.13). If $\theta < 90^\circ$, then there will be hardly any formation of balling, and if $\theta > 90^\circ$ then molten metal will solidify into a ball and adhere to the previous layer [72].

2.3.3.2 Porosities

Porosity is a common type of defect in the L-PBF process. Numerous factors can be responsible for the formation of porosity such as powder induce, solidification of the molten pool, or process-induced. Three types of porosity are common in the L-PBF process [45].

- a) Lack of fusion porosity.
- b) Incomplete melting induced porosity.
- c) Keyhole porosity.

If the volume energy density (VED) is insufficient, then a lack of fusion occurs [52]. This results in non-spherical or irregular porosity in the component. This porosity is frequently found along the grain boundaries between layers, is irregularly shaped, and often contains unmelted powder [67]. Incomplete melting porosities are often induced for the similar reason as lack of fusion. Keyhole porosity is formed at high VED. It creates a vapor capillary that promotes pore formation [73]. Figure 2.14 demonstrates different types of defects [74].

Figure 2.14 Illustration of different types of defects of L-PBF printed parts induced by un-optimized process parameters [74].

High input of energy density creates deeper melt pool and unstable the melt flow which is the key reason for the formation of keyhole porosity [75]. Moreover, the entrapment of the gas and metal powder vaporization is another reason for keyhole porosity formation [76]. Optimized process parameters may avoid porosity in the printed component. Porosity can be reduced by adopting a double laser scan (remelting) strategy [54]. It is a process where multiple laser scans are used on a similar layer. Qiu et al. and Yasa et al. reported that laser remelting strategies increased the density of the finished parts by reducing porosity. It also improved the surface roughness of the printed product [60], [77].

2.3.3.3 Cracks

Another type of defect is known as cracks (Figure 2.14d), which can easily be generated during the L-PBF process. Rapid melting and solidification cycles in successive layers are the root of inconsistent thermal expansion and shrinkage, which causes residual stress. This results in the deformation of the component [50]. Riener et al. demonstrated crack free samples can be produced by preheating [78]. Preheating reduces the thermal difference between the heating and cooling rate. The volume energy density equation (Eq. 2.2) does not include the energy stemming from the substrate heating. As a result, in the current investigation, the energy density equation was adjusted as follows.

$$E_{total} = \frac{P_L + \dot{Q}_p}{V_s \times t \times h} \left[\frac{J}{mm^3} \right] \quad (2.5)$$

Where, E_{total} is the adjusted total energy density and \dot{Q}_p is the heat energy of the powder layer per second (J/s).

$$\dot{Q}_p = mC_p\Delta T/\Delta t \quad (2.6)$$

where, m is the powder mass (g), C_p is heat capacity of the powder, ΔT is the temperature difference of the substrate (T_s) and the powder temperature in the supplier (T_p), and Δt is the time difference from powder deposition to laser deposition on the substrate.

2.4 Powder mixing in L-PBF

Powder mixing in the L-PBF process has gained a lot of attention from researchers. Typically, pre-alloyed powder is used in L-PBF. High quality materials can be produced using pre-alloyed powder [79]. But it experiences some disadvantages like:

- i) Lack of flexibility to modify the alloying elements.
- ii) Limited range of pre-alloyed powders is available for the L-PBF process.

Mixing or blending the powders can solve this problem. Particular alloys can be blended more flexibly with the availability of raw material powders [80]. This avoids the need to store and produces a variety of specific pre-alloyed gas-atomized powders. It is possible to gain significant flexibility in alloy development. Simultaneously, the development and manufacturing of new parts can be expedited significantly [81]. This alternative method can considerably reduce the production costs [82].

Following this methodology, the powder material can be directly modified before the L-PBF process. This influence or improve the characteristics of the final produced part [83]. Previous study showed that produced L-PBF parts using powder mixing achieved a high relative density, which is similar to pre-alloyed powder. In addition, the mechanical properties were found similar or better than those of pre-alloyed powder [83], [84]. Fe-TiB₂ HMS processing is yet to be investigated through powder mixing.

2.5 Metal powder production

The quality of the metal powder is very important for the L-PBF process. Final components quality depends on the atomized metal powder. Different technologies (Figure 2.15) are available for the production of the metal powder [85]. These methods include various types of grinding processes and dispersing the melt by high-pressure (also called atomization) spraying of gas or liquid [86]. In addition, there are some other processes, such as melt spinning, rotating electrode processes, and different types of chemical processes, which are also used to produce metal powders. In present study gas atomized powders are used.

2.5.1 Atomization process

Powder production by gas atomization is well accepted for the L-PBF process. Gas atomization has many advantages, such as it can be used for various types of alloy metals that possess reactive properties in ingots [87]. Also, highly spherical particles can be produced by gas atomization [88].

Figure 2.15 Various methods of metal powder production technology [85]. Considered process routes in this present study is shown in blue color.

The gas atomization process takes place in two steps. In the first step, liquid metal decomposes into small droplets and in the second step is the freezing of these liquid droplets [89]. For the first step, the required energy is supplied by high velocity gas. In the second step, the disintegrated molten droplets try to minimize the surface energy by shaping itself as a sphere. The efficiency of this process depends on the temperature of the molten droplets and surface tension of the liquid metal [90]. The gas atomization technology is classified mainly into two types.

- a) Free fall atomizer (FFA)
- b) Close-coupled atomizer (CCA)

Between FFA and CCA, the CCA (Figure 2.16) is advantageous for metal 3D printing because of the smaller droplet size which results in much finer particles due to the higher gas pressure [91]. Figure 2.16 shows the particle size distribution of FFA and CCA at a constant process parameter [92]. The mass median diameter (d_{50}) of the metal powder by the CCA is in the range of 40 - 80 μm [93].

Figure 2.16 Particle size distribution with free-fall atomizer and close-coupled atomizer [92]. CCA shows smaller size of the particles compared to FFA.

2.5.2 Powder characterization for L-PBF process

The characterization of the powder is essential to determine to ensure powder performance in the machine and final produced parts. Different methods, such as morphology, particle size distribution, flowability, etc. are most commonly used methods to characterize the powders [94].

Morphology and particle size distribution

The morphology of the particles is a very important characteristic that influences the powder flowability and packing density. Particles with irregular shapes typically interlock with each other and resist to flow [95]. Particles with higher sphericity exhibit an even powder distribution over a build platform and result in less porosity and roughness in the final parts. Spherical particles are recommended to use in the L-PBF process [96]. Gas atomized powder with different sizes influenced the quality of the final parts. Finer particles have lower

optical reflectivity and are very easy to melt, however finer particles agglomerate easily [97]. Larger particles demonstrate higher porosity and require high energy input.

Flowability

The flowability of the particles is the spreading ability on the building platform [98]. It is an important factor in the L-PBF process. Different methods are available to determine the flowability of the powders such as hall flow, tap density, angle of repose, Hausner ratio etc. [99]. The hall funnel ($\varnothing = 2.54$ mm) and the carney funnel ($\varnothing = 5$ mm) are the two types of funnels used in the hall flow method [100]. If the powder doesn't flow through the hall funnel, then the carney funnel can be used instead. The flow resistance happens due to the cohesion of the particles [98]. Tap density determines the cohesion properties of the powder and is further used to analyze the theoretical Hausner ratio [99]. Different methods are available to measure the angle of repose. Among them, two methods are widely used, which are: i) static and ii) dynamic. The dynamic angle of repose is used to determine the cohesiveness of the particles and their flow properties [101]. Further details about the flowability measurement will be discussed in chapter 4.

2.6 Summary of the State of the Art

Metal matrix composite is the most promising candidate in materials technology to produce weight saving material. A metal matrix composite is produced by combining two or more components to produce a new material with improved properties. Fe, Mg, Al-based and so on metal matrixes are mostly used in recent times. Among them, the Fe-based metal matrix is popular due to its excellent mechanical properties such as tensile strength, wear resistance, etc. Different reinforcing elements are present such as TiB_2 , SiC, Al_2O_3 , etc. TiB_2 is one of the most promising reinforcing elements because of its high specific modulus and low-density properties. The reinforcing element TiB_2 blended with Fe-matrix creates an excellent Fe- TiB_2 high modulus steel (HMS).

Different approaches were performed to produce Fe- TiB_2 HMS such as conventional casting, spray forming, and additive manufacturing. Slow solidification kinetics in conventional casting showed the formation of coarser particles. However, rapid solidification showed nano-sized TiB_2 precipitation in Fe-matrix by spray forming and additive manufacturing (AM) technology. AM technology is faster, convenient to use, and

has a very high degree of freedom. The laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) process is not well-established AM technologies to produce MMC.

The L-PBF process has gained popularity due to its many advantages such as accuracy, complex geometry, speed, etc. For about a decade, industries like aviation, energy, and the medical sector have been using this technology. With the L-PBF process, it is possible to produce highly dense parts with good mechanical properties. A laser interacts with metal powder to produce parts by the L-PBF process. Laser power fuses the metal powder layer by layer. Different process parameters are available for the L-PBF process. Optimized process parameters produce highly dense parts. Bad process parameters can create different metallurgical problems such as balling, cracks, and porosity. Different approaches can improve the quality of the printed parts. Crack development can be eliminated by using preheating, and porosities can be reduced by using a laser remelting strategy.

The pre-alloyed powder has some disadvantages. This can be eliminated using powder mixing technology. Parts processed by powder mixing similar or better efficiency than pre-alloyed powder. Also, it can reduce the production cost. Furthermore, powder mixing approach in L-PBF technology would enable a new process window in processing metal matrix composites.

Powders required for the L-PBF are produced using gas atomization technology. Since the finished products depend on the numerous powder characteristics, the good quality powder needs to be supplied for the L-PBF process. Close-coupled atomizer (CCA) produces fine and spherical powders which are prerequisites for the L-PBF process.

The processing Fe-TiB₂ HMS has been carried out mainly with pre-alloyed powders. However, the powder mixing approach has yet to be introduced in the Fe-TiB₂ HMS system. Based on the fundamental findings from previous investigations, in the next chapters, the objective and solution approaches of the thesis will be presented.

3 Objective and Outline of the Thesis

The L-PBF process has proven to be a highly effective method for producing high-quality materials, thanks to the technological advancements. From the previous research, it is shown that from the pre-alloyed powder Fe-TiB₂ high-modulus steel (HMS) can be produced by the L-PBF process [4]. The processing of the Fe-TiB₂ using powder mixing is yet to be done. However, the powder mixing strategy has been successful in producing other MMCs. The powder mixing strategy provides flexibility to develop different alloys. Introduction of the powder mixing strategy to produce HMS system and achieving similar properties as pre-alloyed powder may open a new window. Further understanding of the mechanisms in the L-PBF process would provide guidelines for future research and application in the industry. Therefore, the aim of this thesis is to understand the influence of powder mixing strategy in the production of metal matrix composites. The hypothesis of this thesis is:

“It is possible to produce in-situ Fe-TiB₂ metal matrix composite from a mixture of elementary and binary alloy powders by the L-PBF process.”

In-situ reaction will be happened between elementary and binary powder-mixture and produced Fe-TiB₂ MMC. A graphical representation of the powder-mixture for processing in-situ Fe-TiB₂ MMC is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Graphical representation of powder mixing to process in-situ Fe-TiB₂.

In this work, the processing of Fe-TiB₂ (12 vol. %) alloy system will be investigated. Two binary powders (FeB and FeTi) of different alloying compositions will be produced using gas atomization technology. Powder properties such as flowability, morphology is important for the L-PBF process will be investigated. Following powders will be used to make Fe-TiB₂ (12 vol. %).

- i) Pre-alloyed powder: Industry produced powder.
- ii) Powder-mixture: Mixture of two binary powders containing different compositions produced at the University of Bremen.

Samples will be produced by different L-PBF process parameters at room temperature. The quality of the samples will be determined in terms of porosity and cracks. The effect of the process parameters on the melt pool and the shape of the pores will be investigated. A comparison between the printed samples with pre-alloyed powder and powder-mixture will be demonstrated. The microstructural analysis will be investigated. The Reaction between binary powders will be investigated for various laser parameters. Further samples will be produced by involving remelting strategy with substrate preheating (400 °C). Finally, a comparison between single laser scan at room temperature and remelting strategy with substrate preheating will be demonstrated.

Thesis outline

Based on the thesis hypothesis, Figure 3.1 demonstrates the outline of the thesis working process.

Figure 3.2 Graphical outline of the thesis. Powder produced by close-coupled gas atomization. Different powder characterization methods determine the powder properties. Samples printed by the L-PBF process. The effect of the L-PBF process parameters determines by metallographic and microstructure analysis.

4 Methodology and Experiments

This chapter describes the gas atomization procedure of the metal powders. The process used for characterization of the metal powders and producing samples using the L-PBF process is described. Also, the procedure used for characterization and analysis of the printed samples are presented. Afterwards, the printed samples are investigated using different methods. The methodologies used in this study is outlined in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Overview of the used methodology and experimental procedures in this study.

4.1 Close-coupled atomizer (CCA) for powder production

A close-coupled atomizer was used for the production of the powders. To produce binary powder, about three kilograms of feedstock material were charged into the melt chamber. Crucibles made of Al_2O_3 -based ceramic material were used in the melt chamber. The feedstock material was heated to 200 K above its liquidus temperature before atomization and held for 5 minutes inside the crucible to ensure proper melting.

During melting, the protective environment was ensured by argon (Ar) gas. Ar was supplied from a gas cylinder. A stopper rod was used inside the crucible to prevent the melt flowing into the nozzle outlet during the heating process. A pneumatic system mechanically removes the stopper rod moments before the atomization process begins.

The melt temperature was measured by a type B thermocouple, placed in the stopper rod. Another thermocouple type K was placed inside the graphite susceptor, located between the induction coil and the crucible. The atomization gas pressure and melting chamber pressure were recorded. The pouring nozzle was made of ceramic material (HeBoSint O120). The spray tower height is five meters. A cyclone is connected with spray tower to separate particles from the gas. A slit jet type (slit of 0.8 mm) convergent-divergent close-coupled atomizer (CD-CCA-0.8) was used as gas atomizer (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2 Schematic illustrations of the gas atomizer (a) including the close-coupled atomizer (b) [103].

After the atomization, the powder was collected from the bottom of the atomizer. There are some losses of the material during the atomization process due to the formation of splat and flake. Elementary powder and three types of binary powder were produced by this method. Detailed chemical composition is shown in Table 4-1. All the parameters used for the atomization process are listed in Appendix (Table A-1).

First, produced atomized powders were sieved below 250 μm . Afterward, the powders were divided with a vibratory feeder (DR100, Retsch) and a rotating powder divider (PT100, Retsch). The divided powders were collected in eight glass bottles. A representative sample fraction (1/8 of the entire powder) was taken for further analysis.

Table 4-1 Chemical composition (%wt.) of different atomized powder.

Powder	Run No.	Ti	B	Fe
Fe	PA7-295	-	-	bal.
FeB	PA7-296	-	3.66	bal.
FeTi	PA7-297	16.02	-	bal.
FeB	PA7-359	-	8.75	bal.

4.2 Classification and Sieving

After production of the metal powder by the gas atomization process, classification is required to separate the desired size fraction of the particles. Figure 4.3 shows the air classifier used for the classification of the atomized powders. The classifier has various parts, such as dosing channel, ATP classifier, coarse fraction, fine fraction, filter, etc.

The system ran in an inert gas environment in circuit mode. Ar was used to ensure an inert environment. The accessories of the system are gas-tight. The powder (0 - 250 μm) was fed into the feeding channel manually. Then the powder entered the classifier directly with the main air flow. The classifying wheel was driven by a belt drive and a three-phase asynchronous motor. The speed of the sifting wheel was steplessly adjustable via a frequency converter. The sifting air flows through the sifting wheel from the outside to inside and discharges the fine particles into the collector. The coarse particles were rejected by the sifting wheel and flushed with the air flow once again to separate further fine particles. In this way, extremely clean coarse particles were achieved. Five test runs (with 2500 -

5000 rpm) were performed to obtain suitable parameters (Table 4-2). The flow of Ar was fixed at 45 kg/m^3 . The selected rotation speed was set at 3000 rpm to separate $< 20 \mu\text{m}$ particles. The coarse powder was collected from the collector. The final size of the powder was ~ 20 to $250 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4.3 Used air classifier to separate the particle below $20 \mu\text{m}$ (Leibniz-IWT Bremen).

Afterwards, the particle size fraction of $20 - 63 \mu\text{m}$ was separated by sieving. The sieve (mesh size $63 \mu\text{m}$) was placed inside a cylindrical housing. The housing is connected with a motor vibrator. Three conical-shaped chambers were connected with a sieve machine (Figure 4.4). Top conical chamber connected with the valve and powder was fed through that. The valve was left partially open so that the powder flows slowly on the sieve. The vibrator vibrated the entire system. The particles $< 63 \mu\text{m}$ was collected in the bottom conical chamber. The oversized particles ($> 63 \mu\text{m}$) flowed from one side of the sieve and were collected in the other conical chamber.

Table 4-2 Details of test run by air classifier for determining the optimal rotation to separate < 20 μm .

Parameter	Unit	Test run-1	Test run-2	Test run-3	Test run-4	Test run-5
Material	-	FeTiB ₂				
Starting powder mass	g	150	150	150	150	150
Rotation speed (rpm)	rpm	2500	3000	3500	4000	5000
Ar flow	Kg	45	45	45	45	45
Fine powder mass	g	46	27	23	12	11
Fine powder d ₁₀	μm	6.47	5.65	4.94	4.41	3.79
Fine powder d ₅₀	μm	15.07	12.21	10.72	6.92	8.73
Fine powder d ₉₀	μm	24.46	19.77	16.60	12.96	10.22
Coarse powder mass	g	104	123	127	137	139

Figure 4.4 Schematic diagram of the sieving system used in this study to separate the particle below 63 μm .

4.3 Powder characterization for L-PBF

Different characterization parameters of the powder have to be fulfilled before using it in the L-PBF process. The quality of the final product depends on powder characteristics. The important characteristics are particle size distribution, morphology of the particles (shapes or sphericity), and flowability. In this study several powder characterizations have been performed. The outcomes of the experiment will demonstrate whether the powders are suitable for the L-PBF process or not.

4.3.1 Particle size distribution

The particle size distribution (PSD) was determined using laser diffraction system (Mastersizer 2000, Malvern; ISO 13320) for all the powders. This system has an additional accessory (Hydro 2000 G). Hydro 2000 G has a pump and a stirrer. The sieved powders were dispersed with distilled water until the laser obscuration reached in the range of 6 to 9 %. The pump delivered the powder to the optical bench, where the scattering patterns of the particles are detected. A detector array is made up of many individual detectors and is located within the optical bench. These detectors were then used to accurately measure the intensity of light scattered by particles from a range of angles (Figure 4.5). All the detector information was accumulated and recorded in the Malvern software and analyzed the PSD. The Fraunhofer or Mie theory was used by Malvern software. A refractive index of 2.86 was used for iron. Nine measurements for each powder were conducted and averaged. The resulting plots of volume frequency percent vs. particle diameter were determined. One downside of this system is that it assumes all the particles are spherical and can only be used to measure PSD.

Figure 4.5 Measuring principle of the laser diffraction analysis of metal powders.

4.3.2 Morphology measurement

The morphology was determined with an automatic scanning light microscope. The Morphology G3 from Malvern Panalytical was used to determine the sphericity and aspect ratio of the particles. Before starting the procedure, glass plate was cleaned by ethanol carefully to avoid any foreign particles. Afterwards, 2 to 3 mm³ of each powder sample was dispersed on a glass plate. The dispersion of the particles on the glass plate was done by compressed air. The selected pressure for the dispersion was 2.3 bar and the dispersion time was 30 seconds. The light microscope scanned and captured images of the dispersed particles. Subsequently the software algorithm measured the sphericity and aspect ratio of the scanned image and accumulated them into one measurement.

4.3.3 Powder Mixing

The nominal composition of pre-alloyed powder Fe-TiB₂ (12 vol.%) is listed in Table 4-3. The composition was studied with the help of a pseudo-binary Fe-TiB₂ phase diagram presented in Springer et al. [25]. The elemental and binary powder were separated and mixed according to the pre-alloyed powder composition. The mixing was performed by a ball mill (3D-Schüttelmischer Turbula® T2F from Willey A. Bachofen AG) (Figure 4.6) mixture machine. The powders were mixed at a mixing speed of 101 min⁻¹ for two hours. Three mixtures of powder were prepared. Details of the powder-mixture are listed in Table 4-4. After mixing, powder characterization of the powder-mixture was completed to evaluate its flowability.

Table 4-3 Chemical composition of the pre-alloyed Fe-TiB₂ (12 vol.%) powder.

Elements	Ti	B	Fe
Wt%	4.61	1.78	bal.

Figure 4.6 Schematic of the used powder mixture (3D-Schüttelmischer Turbula® T2F).

Table 4-4 Final composition after mixing the powder (Fe-TiB₂ vol.%12).

Run No.	Weight (g)	PA7-295 (Fe)	PA7-296 (FeB – 3.66 wt.%)	PA7-297 (FeTi – 16.02 wt.%)	PA7-359 (FeB – 8.75 wt.%)
Powder-mixture -1 (PM 1)	400	bal.	-	115.11	81.37
Powder-mixture -2 (PM 2)	400	bal.	194.54	115.11	-

4.3.4 Flowability measurements

Four flowability measurement methods were used.

- i) Hall flow (DIN EN ISO 4490) [104]
- ii) Dynamic angle of repose (DIN EN ISO 3953) [105]
- iii) Tap density (DIN EN ISO 3953) [105]
- iv) Hausner ratio

Before flowability measurements, powders were dried in the oven at 200 °C for two hours to remove any residual moisture and cooled down to room temperature. After that, the powders were stored in a desiccator with silica gel pad to absorb moisture to prevent deterioration of the flow properties.

i) Hall Flow

A hall funnel and a carney funnel with opening diameters of 2.54 mm and 5 mm were used for hall flow measurements [98]. For each measurement, 50 g of powder was used. After pouring the powder into the funnel, the powder started to flow through the funnel opening into the cylindrical cup. Subsequently, a stopwatch was used to measure the time. Time begins as soon as the powder begins flowing out of the funnel and stops when all the powder has finished flowing through the funnel. The flow rate value was calculated in units of seconds per gram. It was determined by dividing the measured time taken for all of the powder to exit the funnel by the mass of the powder sample. Five measurements were performed and average value were taken.

ii) Dynamic angle of repose

The dynamic angle of repose α_p was measured to determine the powder's cohesion and flowability properties. If the angle is below 30° , it denotes powder has excellent flowability properties. The angle $\alpha_p > 55^\circ$ represents the powder has limited properties and is not suitable for the L-PBF process. [101]. A clear glass container was filled to two-thirds of its volume with powder. The container was then rotated at a speed of 5 min^{-1} which can be regulated using the voltage regulator shown in Figure 4.7a.

Figure 4.7 Arrangement for measuring dynamic angle of repose (a) measurement of dynamic angle of repose α_p (b).

The glass container was irradiated using transmitted light. The flow inside the container was captured as a video using a digital camera. Images were extracted from the video and then further analyzed by ImageJ software (Figure 4.7b). The dynamic angle of repose was calculated as:

$$\alpha_p = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{H}{R} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

where, H is the perpendicular height of the powder heap and R is the radius of the powder heap.

iii) Tap Density

Cohesion properties are highly dependent on powder density [106]. In general, a powder with high cohesion will stick together creating air packet and a low apparent density. About 50 g powder was filled inside a 25 ml cylinder and the volume was recorded before tapping. This cylinder was placed inside a tapping machine (J Engelsmann AG) and 3000 taps were performed. The volume was recorded once again at the end. Three measurements were conducted for each powder.

iv) Hausner Ratio

It is a theoretical indication of the powder flowability. This is defined as the ratio between tapped density and bulk density [107] of the powder. The ratio is calculated by the following formula:

$$H_R = \frac{\rho_t}{\rho_b} \quad (4.2)$$

where, ρ_t = tapped density [g/cm³] and ρ_b = freely settled bulk density [g/cm³]. A hausner factor between 1.00 to 1.25 is considered as good flowability properties. Hausner ratio above 1.40 considered as the powder has very poor flowability and not suitable for the L-PBF process [99].

4.4 Sample manufacturing via L-PBF process

After powder characterization, the powders were ready for L-PBF processing. The L-PBF process was carried out using the AconityMINI machine from Aconity3D GmbH. This machine can be divided into three major parts:

- i) Printing chamber.
- ii) Control unit.
- iii) Accessory unit.

To begin with, the system was started including control console, PC, and software. Next, the workspace was prepared and cleaned by using a vacuum cleaner and isopropanol. The system was connected to a coolant system. The coating brush was inspected by moving horizontally to avoid collision between the supplier and the building platform. A sandblasted substrate plate was placed on the building platform. Then the powder collector behind the printing chamber was installed before any powder operation. The supplier was filled with the powder (with a supply factor of 3). Afterwards, a Fe-based filter was connected to the system and working chamber cover was installed and fixed with the clamps (Figure 4.8). Then a coupling disk (beam path cover) is connected to laser housing. The optic was moved to the working position. Argon gas was purged inside the printing chamber. When the O₂ level was below 2000 ppm, a blower was started to expedite the interting process.

The desired part file was imported to the software (Figure 4.9). The file contained geometric data such as the layer thickness t , the scanning strategy, and the hatch distance h . In the software, other necessary parameters such as the power P_L , scanning velocity v_s , spot diameter d_L , transport velocity v_t , deposition velocity v_d , and the position of the sample were assigned. A guide beam was used to ensure the position of the samples on the substrate plate before starting the printing process. When the O₂ content level was below 50 ppm, printing was started. During printing the samples, two pyrometers monitored and recorded the temperature of each layer.

Maximum laser power of 350 W was used for manufacturing the samples. The Nd:YAG laser wavelength was $\lambda_L = 1070\text{nm}$. Samples were produced at room temperature and at substrate preheating of 400 °C. To print at substrate preheating temperature, a heater was connected in the building chamber. Substrate plate was installed on the heater. Heating was started when the O₂ level was below 200 ppm. A substrate temperature of 400 °C was maintained for the entire L-PBF process.

Figure 4.8 Printing chamber of AconityMINI 3D from Leibniz-IWT Bremen.

Figure 4.9 Control unit of AconityMINI 3D (Leibniz-IWT Bremen).

After completion of the process, the substrate plate was removed from the building chamber manually (Figure 4.10). The remaining powder were collected by the collector and have been reused. Then a cleaning activity was carried out once again.

Figure 4.10 Building chamber of AconityMINI shows different parts (left) and printed sample AC-381 (PM-1) (right).

4.5 Sample preparation and analysis

The printed sample at room temperature and remelting strategy with substrate preheating were prepared for further analysis. Samples were separated from the substrate plate by high precision wire electrical discharge machining (EDM). Afterwards, these samples were embedded, grounded, polished, and etched for further analysis.

4.5.1 Metallographic sample preparation

For metallographic analysis, the samples were cold embedded (Figure 4.11). The samples were placed into the mould for embedding. The Epofix Resin and Epofix Hardener from Struers were used for embedding. Resin and hardener were mixed in a proportion of 8.3:1 (%wt.) and stirred for two minutes for better mixing. Then this mixture was poured inside the mould and cured for twelve hours. After curing, the sample moulds were ready to grind and polish. The grinding and polishing methods are listed in Table 4-5. The grinding and polishing were completed by Struers Tegramin-25 (Figure 4.12). Polishing steps were

repeated if the scratch still presents in the sample. The grounded surface was polished by diamond polishing suspension at varying loads.

Figure 4.11 a) Cold embedding of printed samples b) polished samples prepared for metallographic analysis.

Table 4-5 Details of the grinding and polishing steps of the printed samples.

Steps no.	Experiment steps	Polishing solution	Polishing duration (min)
1	SiC foil #220	Water	4
2	SiC foil #800	Water	4
3	SiC foil #1200	Water	3
4	MD Allegro	Diapro 9 μm	8
5	MD Dac	Diapro 3 μm	6
6	MD Nap	Diapro 1 μm	6
7	MD Chem	OP-S Nondry	2

Figure 4.12 Schematic of grinding and polishing machine (Struers Tegramin-25).

4.5.2 Defect analysis

Unoptimized process parameters are responsible for the formation of defects [108]–[111]. Different types of defects were discussed in section 2.3.3.2. Polished samples were analyzed using bright field (BF), dark field (DF), and Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) respectively. Samples were analyzed under the light microscope (Carl Zeiss, Axio Imager 2). The microscope scanned multiple areas of the sample and stitched them together to produce a final image. Images were further analyzed by ImageJ software. The images were converted to 8-bit and binarized using a contrast-dependent threshold value. The software algorithm calculated defect value (%) and mean shape of porosities. Figure 4.13 shows the optical microscopy image and threshold contrasted binary image.

4.5.3 Heat map

AconityMINI 3D machine has two pyrometers. During the L-PBF process, the pyrometers recorded the temperature of each layer. A python script was used to analyze recorded pyrometer data at different sample heights.

Figure 4.13 Porosity analysis by ImageJ software (a) optical microscopy image (b) binarized image. Run no. AC-381 (PM-1).

4.5.4 Melt pool analysis

The size of the melt pool (Figure 4.14) depends on the laser parameters. Moreover, the overlaps between melt pools determine the quality of the sample [112]–[114]. The polished samples were etched by Nital (HNO_3 of 3% solution in ethanol) for about 30 seconds. Then it was rinsed with alcohol and dried. Finally, the sample was placed under the optical microscope. Images were analyzed using bright field (BF), dark field (DF), and Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) respectively. The melt pool depth was investigated from those images by ImageJ software.

Figure 4.14 Melt pool geometric feature after etching by Nital (HNO_3 of 3% solution in ethanol).

4.5.5 SEM and EDX

The sample was ground, polished and etched before scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX) investigation. For microstructural analysis, surface quality and particle morphology SEM (Carl Zeiss, SUPRA 40) is used. To know the composition of the material and element mapping was done by EDX (Bruker XFlash 6/30 EDX detector).

4.5.6 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is used to determine qualitative and quantitative analyses of the crystalline phases in the material [115]. XRD utilises the principle that x-rays are either scattered or absorbed by an object. In this study, the sample was grounded, polished and etched before XRD investigation. Quantitative phase analysis was performed on the diffractometer D8 advance A25-X1 with a Co Ka X-ray source.

5 Result and Discussion

In this chapter, the entire investigation results are presented. The metal powders are atomized by close-coupled atomizer (CCA) and the powder further characterized. The flowability of the powder is investigated and discussed. The L-PBF process parameters is studied. The samples are printed at room temperature and at substrate preheating temperature of 400 °C. The printed samples are further investigated by analyzing defects (e.g., porosity, crack), effects of process parameters, melt pool analysis, microstructure analysis. The obtained results after the investigation are discussed here. Finally, a comparison between room temperature single laser scan and remelting strategy with substrate preheating is presented and discussed.

5.1 Powder production

Pure element such as B, Ti, V, Cr, etc. has a higher melting temperature, which is a disadvantage for gas atomization technology. The melting temperatures of B and Ti are 2076 °C and 1668 °C, respectively, which is higher than the maximum capacity (up to 1750 °C) of the melting system used for this work (PA7 University of Bremen). The maximum capacity of the used crucible is 1750 °C, which is a limitation of melting technology. Moreover, the differences in densities of pure elements are another limitation. The density of Ti and B is 4.5 g/cm³ and 2.34 g/cm³ respectively, which is lower than the density of Fe (7.87 g/cm³) (Table 5-1). Higher differences in densities can causes separation of the powder in the mixture. Therefore, the binary powder is suitable. Binary powder Fe-B and Fe-Ti provides the flexibility to make different volume fraction of mixture.

In this work, FeB, where, B contains 3.66 wt.% and 8.75 wt.%, and FeTi, where Ti contains 16.02 wt.%, are produced based on the phase diagram. According to the Fe-B binary phase diagram (Figure 5.1), when the B content is about 4 wt.%, the melting temperature of the Fe-B alloy is the lowest ~ 1174 °C. As also illustrated in Figure 5.1, a further increase in B content above 4 wt.% causes an increase in the melting point of the Fe-B alloy. For instance, B content of ~ 8.75 wt.% has a liquidus temperature of ~ 1400 °C, which is also well below 1750 °C. Therefore, these two combinations have been selected for atomization.

Similarly, for the Fe-Ti phase diagram (Figure 5.2), the Ti content of ~ 16 wt.% has a liquidus temperature of ~ 1280 °C. Based on this melting temperature, atomization parameters (see Table A-1) have been selected for producing binary alloy.

Table 5-1 Melting temperatures and densities of different materials.

Element/alloy	Melting temperature T_m [°C]	Density [g/cm ³]
Fe	1538	7.87
Ti	1668	4.5
B	2076	2.34
Fe-B	1172 (Eutectic)	~ 7
Fe-Ti	1330 (Eutectic)	~ 6.54

Figure 5.1 Fe-B phase diagram shows the melting temperature for different wt.% of B [116].

Figure 5.2 Fe-Ti phase diagram shows the melting temperature for different wt.% of Ti [117].

5.2 Powder Characterization

In the L-PBF process, it is recommended to use powder size fraction of 20 – 63 μm [118]. The particle size distribution (PSD) provides information about the size of the particles after sieving. Figure 5.3 shows the particle size distribution of the classified particles (20 – 63 μm). The particle size distribution value is calculated in three percentiles, which are d_{10} , d_{50} , and d_{90} . The d_{10} and d_{90} values represent the diameters for which 10% and 90% of the powders are smaller than the given value. PSD analysis revealed that the sizes of the particles are between 20 – 63 μm (Table 5-2), which fulfills the pre-requirements for the L-PBF process. The size of the powder-mixtures has not been quantified as it is achieved from a mixture of previously classified elementary (Fe) and binary powders (Fe-B, Fe-Ti).

Figure 5.3 Particle size distribution of different powders (size fraction 20 – 63 μm) for L-PBF process.

Table 5-2 Powder characterization (PSD and morphology) of different powders.

Powder ID Powder characteristics	d_{10}	d_{50}	d_{90}	Avg. circularity	Avg. AR_{50}
PA7-295 (Fe)	22.19	38.42	62.60	0.93	0.84
PA7-296 (FeB-3.66 wt.%)	25.27	44.14	62.59	0.87	0.79
PA7-297 (FeTi-16.02 wt.%)	19.03	41.84	54.96	0.95	0.88
PA7-359 (FeB-8.75 wt.%)	31.01	44.49	63.2	0.87	0.74
S0213 (Pre-alloyed)	19.49	35.57	54.97	0.86	0.71

The shape of the particles substantially influences powder flowability. Particles of an irregular shape can cause agglomeration, decreases powder packing efficiency, and reduces powder flowability [119]. Figure 5.4a shows, FeB – 3.66 wt.% (PA7-296) has the lowest circularity value of 0.85 and FeTi - 16.02 wt.% (PA7-297) has the highest circularity value of 0.95. The average circularity of the gas atomized powders is around 0.85 – 0.95, which can be considered almost spherical. Figure 5.4b shows the average aspect ratio

(AR_{50}) of different powders. It is the ratio of the width and the height of the particles. From a static condition, the variation of the AR_{50} can affect the flowability of the powders as it describes the shape of the particle [120]. Higher AR_{50} values suggest the particles are more spherical, i.e., the particles move past one another and flow more easily. Spherical particles tend to pack more densely compared with irregularly shaped particles that have low AR_{50} [121]. Lower AR_{50} represents the shape of the particles are distorted and increases the resistivity of the flowability. The maximum $AR_{50} = 0.88$ for FeTi - 16.02 wt.% (PA7-297) and the minimum $AR_{50} = 0.71$ for FeB - 3.66 wt.% (PA7-296) are found. The AR_{50} values of the powders used in this study are between 0.71 – 0.88, which is suitable for the L-PBF process.

Figure 5.4 Morphology of the powder (size fraction 20 – 63 μm) (a) circularity (b) aspect ratio.

From SEM images (Figure 5.5), the morphology of the various powders can be further distinguished. A few satellite structures are visible in the SEM images and the shape is predominantly spherical in laboratory-scale powder (produced in PA7, University of Bremen). Slightly distorted shaped particles are observed in industrial-scale powder (S0213 – Pre-alloyed). A Map data of powder-mixtures are generated by EDX. The elemental mapping shows a homogeneous distribution of the elements in powder-mixtures (see Figure 5.6).

Finally, a comparison between pre-alloyed powder (run no. S0213, produced by Rosswag GmbH) and Fe, FeB, and FeTi are listed in Table 5-2. PSD and morphology of the powders are comparable to pre-alloyed powder.

Figure 5.5 SEM images of gas atomized metal powders. (a-d) – lab-scale powders (produced in University of Bremen) (e) industrial-scale powder (produced in Rosswag GmbH) (f-g) powder-mixtures.

Figure 5.6 EDX map data image revealed elemental distribution of Fe, Ti, and B where (a) powder-mixture 1 (PM-1) (b) powder-mixture 2 (PM-2)

5.3 Flowability analysis

Powder flowability processes has been described in section 4.3.4. Flowability of the powders are measured after conducting a Hall-flow test using the hall funnel ($\varnothing = 2.54$ mm) and the carney funnel ($\varnothing = 5$ mm). The values are listed in Table 5-3. The mean values from five Hall-flow measurements have been considered. FeB-3.66 wt.% (PA7-296), FeB-8.75 wt.% (PA7-359), and PM-2 didn't flow through the hall funnel ($\varnothing = 2.54$ mm). The circularity and aspect ratio of PA7-296 and PA7-359 have the lowest values, which could be the reason of lower flowability (see Table 5-2). Irregular shaped powder reduces the powder flowability by increasing the cohesive force [95]. This doesn't allow these two powders to flow through the hall funnel.

Table 5-3 Flowability measurements of different powders.

Powder ID	Alloy	Hall flow FR _h /50g $\varnothing = 2.54$ mm	Carney flow FR _c /50g $\varnothing = 5$ mm	Bulk density ρ_b [g/cm ³]	Tapped density ρ_t [g/cm ³]	Hausner ratio H _R [-]	Avg. AOR [^o]
PA7-295	Fe	6.46	1.07	4.08	4.76	1.17	42.67 ± 2.86
PA7-296	FeB-3.66 wt.%	0	2.21	4.08	4.57	1.12	41.46 ± 0.63
PA7-297	FeTi- 16.02 wt.%	23.82	1.09	4.29	4.76	1.11	37.23 ± 2.21
PA7-359	FeB-8.75 wt.%	0	1.54	3.92	4.65	1.19	40.76 ± 3.16
PM-1	Fe+FeB- 8.75+FeTi	9.68	1.88	4.00	4.72	1.18	41.40 ± 2.59
PM-2	Fe+FeB- 3.66+FeTi	0	1.51	4.08	4.65	1.14	41.60 ± 2.18
S0213	Pre- alloyed	7.01	1.70	4.03	4.80	1.19	37.86 ± 0.97

In hall flow measurements, PA7-295 has good flowability of $FR_h = 6.46$ s/ 50g for the hall funnel ($\varnothing = 2.54$ mm). On the other hand, the values for the carney funnel are almost identical for each powder. Although, the shape of S0213 is slightly distorted (see Figure 5.5). However, the powder shows identical flowability as lab-scale powders. For powder-mixtures (PM-1 and PM-2), the carney funnel value is $FR_c = 1.88$ s/ 50g and 1.51 s/ 50g, respectively. Agglomeration of the powders has been found before conducting the experiment. Presence of the residual moisture is the key reason for agglomeration. This was avoided by drying in the oven for two hours at 200 °C. The bulk density and the tapped density were measured for each powder (Figure 5.7). The lowest value of bulk density $\rho_b = 3.92$ g/cm³ observed for FeB-8.75 wt.% (PA7-359) powder (see Table 5-3). Fe (PA7-295) powder has the highest tapped density $\rho_t = 4.76$ g/cm³. Hausner ratio is calculated from the bulk and tapped density values of the powders (Figure 5.8). The maximum value of 1.19 is found for FeB-8.75 wt.% (PA7-359) and pre-alloyed FeTiB₂ (12 vol.%) [S0213] powders. For FeTi-16.02 wt.% (PA7-297) powder the haunser ratio is 1.11, which is the minimum value to be found. The powder mixtures, PM-1 and PM-2 possess a value of 1.18 and 1.14, respectively. Hausner ratio results indicates that lab-scale and industry-scale powder has good flow properties, which is below 1.25.

Figure 5.7 Measure tapped density for atomized powder, powder-mixture, and pre-alloyed powder.

Figure 5.9 shows the dynamic angle of repose of the used powders in the present study. The average dynamic angle of repose of PM-1 is 41.40° and for PM 2 is 41.60°, which are almost identical. The FeTi-16.02 wt.% (PA7-297) powder has the lowest dynamic angle of repose value of 37.23°. Pre-alloyed (FeTiB₂– 12 vol.%) [S0213] powder shows similar result as lab-scale powder. The dynamic angle of repose above 55° shows sluggish, very high cohesiveness, and has very limited flow. [101]. The average dynamic angle of repose was

found $37^{\circ} - 43^{\circ}$, which reflects the good flowability properties of the powders for the L-PBF process.

Figure 5.8 Measured Hausner ratio of the atomized powder, powder-mixture, and pre-alloyed powder.

Figure 5.9 Measured dynamic angle of repose atomized powder, powder-mixture, and pre-alloyed powder.

Summary: Powder characterization investigations demonstrated that the particle size distribution and morphology of gas atomized powders satisfied the requirements for the L-PBF process. SEM images revealed the sphericity of the particles, and EDX images revealed the homogeneous distribution after mixing the powders. Industry-scale (S0213) powder has slight distortion in shape compared to the lab-scale powders. However, it exhibits good flowability. Flowability of distinct powders demonstrated satisfactory performance as well as powder-mixtures. Hardly any agglomeration of the particles (dried for 2 hours at 200°C) was observed during the experiment.

5.4 L-PBF process parameters

After the powder characterization and the flowability measurements, powders are ready for the L-PBF process. The quality of the printed sample highly depends on the L-PBF process parameters. The average laser absorptance of Fe for Nd:YAG laser is about 0.64 [122]. Bonesso et al. investigated that the laser absorptance by metal powder is increased upto 0.74 after increasing laser power [97]. Higher absorptance means the loss of laser energy by reflection and transmission are lower. Ovcharenko et al. calculated the thermal effects for the reactions of titanium diboride formation from ferro-alloys [123].

Based on the absorption of metal powder and thermal effects for the reaction of TiB_2 formation, the L-PBF process parameters are selected. Parameter selected for single laser scan at room temperature listed in Table 5-4. It is noted that, the selected process parameters are higher than the required reaction energy to form TiB_2 so that the metal powder melted properly.

Table 5-4 L-PBF process parameters at room temperature (~ 20 °C).

Parameters	AC-335	AC-336	AC-338
Powder ID	S0213	PM-1	PM-2
Alloy	FeTiB ₂ (12 vol.%)	Fe+FeB (8.75)+FeTi (16.02)	Fe+FeB (3.66)+FeTi (16.02)
Laser power P_L	250,300,350	250,300,350	250,300,350
Scanning velocity v_s	700,800,900	700,800,900	700,800,900
Hatch h	80 μm	80 μm	80 μm
Laser spot diameter d_L	80 μm	80 μm	80 μm
Layer thickness t	50 μm	50 μm	50 μm
Supply factor	3	3	3
Scanning strategy	Bi-directional (90°)	Bi-directional (90°)	Bi-directional (90°)
Deposition velocity	100	100	100
Transport velocity	150	150	150

5.5 L-PBF samples analysis

Samples printed at room temperature using single laser scan are AC-335 (pre-alloyed), AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2). To understand the influence of the process parameters the printed samples are further investigated. The printed samples are embedded, grounded, polished and etched and analysed using optical microscope. Cracks, porosity, and melt pool depth are quantified from optical microscopy images. Furthermore, microstructures are investigated by SEM and EDX. To identify the phase a XRD investigation is carried out.

5.5.1 Defects analysis

Different types of defects in the L-PBF samples are described in section 2.3.3.2. Unoptimized process parameters are responsible for the formation of those defects in the samples. This is one of the major drawbacks of the L-PBF process. The samples AC-335 (pre-alloyed), AC-336 (PM-1), and AC-338 (PM-2) are printed at room temperature. The optical microscope images are analyzed by ImageJ software, which revealed porosities and cracks in the sample. Figure 5.10 demonstrates the development of porosities and cracks in the printed samples AC-335 (pre-alloyed). The macro-sized cracks are initiated from the bottom and side edges of the samples. Along with those, micro-sized cracks are present within the samples. During the melting process, the melt pool has the highest temperature and the melt pool will expand. On the other hand, the area further away from the melt pool has a lower temperature and will not expand. Due to the difference in temperatures, internal stress develops around the melt pool, which is finally released in the form of cracks [124]. Lack of fusion porosities and keyhole porosities are visible in the microscopy images. Lower laser power of 250 W shows high fraction of lack of porosity in AC-335 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.10). However, lack of fusion porosity in AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.11) and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.12) is highly visible for all the used laser powers and scan velocities. Lack of fusion porosity is inducing due to the insufficient overlapping of the melt pool. Partially melted powder is also another reason to form lack of fusion porosity. Keyhole porosities are also visible for all printed samples. Higher energy density is responsible for inducing keyhole porosity [52]. The quantitative analysis of these porosities will be discussed in next section 5.5.2.

Figure 5.10 Threshold contrasted optical microscope images of L-PBF sample AC-335 (pre-alloyed). The formation of crack is started from the bottom and side edges of the samples. Different types of defects are presents in the samples.

Figure 5.11 Threshold contrasted optical microscope images of L-PBF sample AC-336 (PM-1). The formation of crack is started from the bottom and side edges of the samples. Different types of porosities are presents in the samples.

Figure 5.12

Threshold contrasted optical microscope images of L-PBF sample AC-338 (PM-2). The formation of crack is started from the bottom and side edges of the. Different types of defects are present in the samples.

5.5.2 Effect of the process parameters

The fraction of defects is evaluated quantitatively for different process parameters. Figure 5.13a shows the area percentage of defects in as-printed samples AC-335 (pre-alloyed) at different laser power and scanning velocity. With increasing laser power, the amount of defect increases. At a laser power of 350 W and scanning velocity of 700 mm/s, AC-336 (PM-1) has higher defects of about 10.94% (Figure 5.13b), which is three times higher than AC-335 (pre-alloyed). AC-338 (PM-2) has around 7.99% of defects at same condition (Figure 5.13c), which is about two times higher than AC-335 (pre-alloyed). The value of the defects varies significantly because of the formation of macro-sized cracks in the samples.

Figure 5.13 L-PBF samples at different process parameters; (a-c) fraction of defects, (d) relationship between amount of defect and volume energy density.

AC-335 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.13a) has about 5.69% defects at a laser power of 250 W and scanning velocity of 800 mm/s. Laser power 300 W and scanning velocity 700 mm/s having almost identical fractions of defects for AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2). Increasing scanning velocity reduces the amount of defect in AC-335 (pre-alloyed) and AC-338 (PM-2). However, AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.13b) shows an inconsistent percentage of defects at different laser scanning velocity. This is also causing primarily due to the presence of macro-sized cracks. However, lack of fusion porosity is also another reason (see Figure 5.11).

The fraction of defects was also analyzed with respect to volume energy density (VED). The relationship of volume energy density with different process parameters has been described in section 2.3.1. The fraction of defects is higher in high energy density (125 J/mm^3) for both AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.13d) due the presence of macro-sized cracks (Figure 5.10 and Figure 5.12). AC-335 (pre-alloyed) shows a similar fraction of defects at the range of $83 \text{ J/mm}^3 - 125 \text{ J/mm}^3$. At the lowest VED (78 J/mm^3), the highest amount of defect is observable for AC-335 (pre-alloyed) due to the presence of higher amount lack of fusion porosity (Figure 5.10).

From the metallographic images, the shape of the porosity is investigated. The shape of the porosity is highly influenced by the VED. Most cracks are non-spherical in shape. Considering the average circularity size of 0.4 – 1.0 to avoid the cracks, shape of the porosity is measured. High laser power demonstrates many spherical pores in AC-335 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.14a). The mean circularity of the pores at a laser power of 350W and scanning velocity of 700 mm/s is 0.92, which suggests that the lack of fusion is less prevalent in AC-335 (pre-alloyed). AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2) demonstrate more or less similar mean circularity for all parameters which suggests lack of fusion is still dominant here. The average sphericity of the porosity is 0.72 – 0.82 for AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.14b) and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.14c). Increasing energy density (Figure 5.14d) shows similar trend for all the samples. The sphericity of the porosity increases as the volume energy density increases, which means lack of fusion porosities are reducing. Laser energy above 100 J/mm^3 shows the consistent increment in the porosity sphericity. An optimized parameter such as increasing laser power or changing hatch distance may reduce the lack of fusion hence improving the quality of the sample [112].

Figure 5.14 Influence of the process parameters on; (a-c) shape of the porosity (d) relationship between mean circularity of the pores and volume energy density.

5.5.3 Heat map

Figure 5.15 shows the surface temperature of different layers up to 3 mm sample height. The pyrometer signals display the similar values at a certain layer for three runs. The similarities in pyrometer values at a certain layer indicates similar cooling condition. Moreover, the pyrometer signal suggests that the conditions inside the building chamber was identical during printing the samples AC-335 (pre-alloyed), AC-336 (PM-1), and AC-338 (PM-2).

Figure 5.15 Surface temperature signal of the samples at different layers recorded by pyrometer.

5.5.4 Melt pool analysis

The melt pool depth is evaluated by examining the cross-sections that had been etched with 3% Nital solution. Porosity of the printed samples also can be explained in terms of melt pool depth. Higher volume energy density changes the shape of the melt pool to a narrow and elongated form, which is sometimes responsible for keyhole porosity. During melt pool analysis, lack of fusion is also observed (Figure 5.16a) specially between the overlapping of laser scanning between two layers due to the large hatch distance and lower laser power. The depth of the melt pool is found almost similar in the starting scanning line at higher volume energy density. This indicates the generation of homogeneous melt pool depth (Figure 5.16 and Figure 5.17b). The non-homogeneity melt pool is observed at lower volume energy density, which is found mostly at the edge of the printed samples due to the formation of waviness (Figure 5.16c). The waviness formed due to the expansion and shrinkage of the melt pool while a large temperature difference is present [125].

Figure 5.16 Characteristics of melt pool a) lack of fusion porosity and keyhole porosity b) homogeneous molten pool at the middle of the sample c) non-homogeneous molten pool at the edge.

Furthermore, the melt pool depth at different process parameters is measured. It should be noted that the depth of the melt pool measurement differs by a standard deviation of $\sim 19 \mu\text{m}$ due to an error in the melt pool edge detection. Figure 5.17a shows the melt pool depth for pre-alloyed (AC-335) sample. Increasing laser power increases the melt pool depth as the energy density and laser power have a proportional relation. The highest melt pool depth is to be found $256 \mu\text{m}$ for AC-335 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.17a). Moreover, the scanning velocity has an influence on melt pool depth generation. Higher scanning velocity means the laser exposure time at a particular position is shorter. As scanning velocity increases the melt pool depth decreases for AC-335 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.16a). AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.17 and Figure 5.16b) and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.17c) show almost similar melt pool depth generation for the laser power and the scanning velocity. The melt pool depth increases about 30% at a laser power of 350 W compared to the lower laser power of 250W for AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.17b). The depth of the melt pool varied with respect to the volume energy density (VED). As seen in Figure 5.17d, lower VED has the lowest depth of melt pool. The melt pool depth increases linearly, followed by the VED. At 125 J/mm^3 shows the highest melt pool depth for all three samples.

Figure 5.17 Influence of the process parameters on; (a-c) melt pool depth (d) relationship between melt pool depth and volume energy density.

5.5.5 Microstructure

The formation of TiB_2 in Fe-matrix from pre-alloyed powder is already investigated by L-PBF process (see Figure 2.4c). However, the processing of the Fe- TiB_2 by powder mixing is yet to be done. Based on that observation a ***hypothesis: “it is possible to produce in-situ Fe- TiB_2 metal matrix composite from a mixture of elementary and binary alloy powders by L-PBF process”*** has been proposed. In this section, hypothesis is investigated and discussed in detail. The binary alloy powder used in this present study for the processing of Fe- TiB_2 via L-PBF process is listed in Table 4-4. To identify the formation of the TiB_2 particles in the Fe-matrix, microstructure analysis was performed. SEM images demonstrated the microstructure images of the printed sample AC-335 (pre-alloyed), AC-336 (PM-1), and AC-338 (PM-2). Table 5-5 contains details about the L-PBF parameters

chosen for SEM investigation. AC-335 (pre-alloyed) shows that nano-scaled darker particles are formed in the ferritic matrix (Figure 5.18). The samples from AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2) with powder-mixtures show similar microstructural formation as AC-335 (pre-alloyed). Between AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.19) and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.20), AC-336 (PM-1) shows a higher amount of dark particle formation due to the difference in binary powder alloying type. The size of nano-scaled dark particles ranges from 40 to 120 nm. SEM images also demonstrates homogenized dark particles distribution along the grain boundaries for all the analysed samples. The precipitated nano-sized particles are mostly spherical and identical for all analysed samples. In addition, higher volume energy density shows and elevated fraction of dark particles formation.

Table 5-5 Parameters of the samples chosen for SEM and EDX investigation.

Sample No.	Alloy	1 st sample Laser	2 nd sample Laser	Scanning	Hatch <i>H</i> [μm]
		power P_L [W]	power P_L [W]	velocity v_s [mm/s]	
AC-335	Pre-alloyed	300	350	700	80
AC-336	Fe+FeB-8.75+FeTi-16.02	300	350	700	80
AC-338	Fe+FeB-3.66+FeTi-16.02	300	350	700	80

Figure 5.18 Detailed microstructure analysis of an as-printed sample AC-335 (pre-alloyed). SEM images for (a, c) volume energy density 107 J/mm^3 (b, d) volume energy density 125 J/mm^3 .

Figure 5.19 Detailed microstructure analysis of as-printed sample AC-336 (PM-1). SEM images for (a, c) volume energy density 107 J/mm³ (b, d) volume energy density 125 J/mm³.

Figure 5.20 Detailed microstructure analysis of as-printed sample AC-338 (PM-2). SEM images for (a, c) volume energy density 107 J/mm³ (b, d) volume energy density 125 J/mm³.

Furthermore, grain size and morphology have been analyzed for higher volume energy density of 125 J/mm^3 by ImageJ software. The average size of the grain of AC-335 (pre-alloyed) is about $0.65 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 5.21b). The grain size of the AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2) is almost similar as AC-335 (pre-alloyed). The measured grain size of AC-336 (PM-1) is about $0.71 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 5.22b) and AC-338 (PM-2) is about $0.61 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 5.23b). The grain growth rate was almost identical for three samples. To reflect the columnarity in grain morphology, the aspect ratio of the grain was calculated, which is defined as the grain length ratio between the major and minor axes of the grains. The average aspect ratio of AC-335 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.21c), AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.22c), and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.23c) are about 1.29, 1.30, and 1.30, respectively. The aspect ratio suggesting similar morphological characteristics (nearly equiaxed) among the printed samples with different powders.

Figure 5.21 AC-335 (pre-alloyed) at volume energy density 125 J/mm^3 where (a) SEM (b) grain size (c) aspect ratio.

Figure 5.22 AC-336 (PM-1) at volume energy density 125 J/mm^3 where (a) SEM (b) grain size (c) aspect ratio.

Figure 5.23 AC-338 (PM-2) at volume energy density 125 J/mm^3 where (a) SEM (b) grain size (c) aspect ratio.

In order to identify the distribution of elements printed sample, EDX measurement was performed. The presence of Fe, Ti, and B are shown in different colors. Figure 5.24 shows the elemental distribution of AC-335 (pre-alloyed) sample and it shows Ti and B elements are concentrated on the grain boundaries. Similar concentration is found for AC-336 (PM-1) (Figure 5.25) and AC-338 (PM-2) (Figure 5.26). The concentration of Ti and B in the ferritic matrix could be the indication of the presence of TiB_2 in Fe-matrix.

Figure 5.24 EDX mapping data of AC-335 (pre-alloyed) shows the presence of Ti and B in grain boundaries.

Figure 5.25 EDX mapping data of AC-336 (PM-1) shows the presence of Ti and B in grain boundaries.

Figure 5.26 EDX mapping data of AC-338 (PM-2) shows the presence of Ti and B in grain boundaries.

Summary: At room temperature, all the samples formed macro-sized cracks due to the large thermal gradient. Lower power shows a lack of fusion porosity. The circularity of the porosity is similar for both AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2). In addition, AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2) showed a higher fraction of defects at high volume energy density. The heat map showed the signal was consistent for up to 3 mm sample height. The defects of the material are highly dependent on melt pool characteristics. Lack of overlapping between the melt pool is the key reason for the formation of lack of fusion. Higher volume energy showed keyhole porosity formation, whereas lower energy density showed the formation of lack of fusion porosity. The melt pool depth increases higher with increasing volume energy density. After analyzing the SEM images, a homogeneous distribution of dark particles was revealed in the Fe-matrix which is similar to the pre-alloyed samples (AC-335). The obtained outcome supports the proposed hypothesis that the processing of Fe-TiB₂ MMC from powder-mixture via L-PBF process is possible. The formation of this nano-sized particles is found mostly along the grain boundaries. Higher power shows more precipitation than lower power due to its high melting capability with different powders. The mean grain size and morphology are similar for printed samples at room temperature. EDX images revealed the concentration of Ti and B in the grain boundaries. XRD graph confirms the existence of α -Fe, but TiB₂ phase could not be identified.

5.6 Remelting at room temperature

Due to the formation of cracks and porosity, a remelting strategy was adopted at room temperature. The selected L-PBF parameters for remelting runs are listed in Table 5-6. Material with high volume energy density i.e., large heating and cooling difference deforms it heavily, which prevents it from building uniformly (Figure 5.30) and samples distorted easily. Moreover, the development of internal stress is very high due to the large thermal gradient. The internal stress is finally released in the forms of cracks and distorted the printed samples. Due to its poor building, quantitative analysis was not carried out for the printed samples. No further printing run was carried out using remelting strategy at room temperature due to its high deformation and delamination of layers.

Table 5-6 Process parameter selection for double laser scan (remelting) strategy at room temperature.

Parameters	AC-374
Powder ID	PM-1
Alloy	Fe+FeB (8.75)+FeTi (16.02)
1 st Laser power $P_{L,1}$	200,250,300
2 nd Laser power $P_{L,2}$	25%, 50%,75% of 1 st laser power
1 st Scanning velocity $v_{s,1}$	700
2 nd Scanning velocity $v_{s,2}$	1000
Hatch h	80 μm
Laser spot diameter d_L	80 μm
Layer thickness t	50 μm
Scan strategy	Bi-directional (90°)

Figure 5.30 Deform sample (AC-374) building for remelting strategy at room temperature where (a) top view (b) side view.

5.7 Remelting with substrate preheating

Remelting at room temperature demonstrates poor building of the samples. Therefore, substrate preheating is introduced with remelting. In this section, the result obtained by applying remelting strategy with substrate preheating of 400 °C will be discussed. The process parameters are listed in Table 5-7.

Table 5-7 Process parameter selection for substrate preheating (400 °C) with remelting strategy.

Parameters	AC-380	AC-381
Powder ID	S0213	PM-1
Alloy	FeTiB ₂ (12 vol.%)	Fe+FeB (8.75)+FeTi (16.02)
1 st Laser power $P_{L,1}$	200,250,300	200,250,300
2 nd Laser power $P_{L,2}$	25%, 50%,75% of 1 st laser power	25%, 50%,75% of 1 st laser power
1 st Scanning velocity $v_{s,1}$	700	700
2 nd Scanning velocity $v_{s,2}$	1000	1000
Hatch h	80 μ m	80 μ m
Laser spot diameter d_L	80 μ m	80 μ m
Layer thickness t	50 μ m	50 μ m
Supply factor	3	3
Scanning strategy	Bi-directional (90°)	Bi-directional (90°)
Deposition velocity	100	100
Transport velocity	150	150

5.7.1 Defect analysis and effect of the process parameters

The samples printed by remelting strategy with substrate preheating is investigated by light microscope. At lower laser power of 200 W (Figure 5.31 and Figure 5.32), sample has cracks and irregular porosities. The macro-sized cracks are initiated from the side edges of the samples. Increasing laser power reduces the porosity and cracks AC-380 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.31). At a laser power of 300 W in AC-380 (pre-alloyed) samples hardly any cracks are found from the bottom of the sample; however, the porosities are still in the samples. Similarly, AC-381 (PM-1) samples (Figure 5.32) shows hardly any cracks developed from the bottom of the samples at the same process parameters. Substrate preheating reduces the thermal gradient and the internal stress in the samples, which eliminates the cracks from the samples. The porosities are also improved after remelting the printed layers. Increasing second scan laser power decreases the fraction of porosities for both AC-380 (pre-alloyed) samples (Figure 5.31) and AC-381 (PM-1) (Figure 5.32). The samples without cracks (blue border) are shown in Figure 5.31, and their parameters are noted in Table 5-8.

Figure 5.31

Substrate preheating (400 °C) with remelting strategy demonstrates an improved printed AC-380 (pre-alloyed) sample. Blue border represents the crack free samples.

Figure 5.32 Substrate preheating (400 °C) with remelting strategy demonstrates an improved printed AC-381 (PM-1) sample. Blue border represents the crack free samples.

Table 5-8 Detailed parameter description where no cracks found in the sample at 400 °C preheating temperature.

Sample no.	1 st scan laser power $P_{L,1}$ [W]	2 nd scan laser power $P_{L,1}$ [W]	1 st scan laser velocity $V_{s,1}$ [mm/s]	2 nd scan laser velocity $V_{s,1}$ [mm/s]	Hatch distance H [μm]
AC-380	250	187.5	700	1000	80
	350	75, 150, 225	700	1000	80
AC-381	250	125	700	1000	80
	350	75, 150, 225	700	1000	80

Figure 5.33a and Figure 5.33b demonstrates the fraction of defects in the samples. The defect percentage for AC-380 (pre-alloyed) samples (Figure 5.33a) is between 2 to 3%. Increasing the second scan laser power decreases the amount of defect of the samples (AC-380 and AC-381). First laser power ($P_{L,1}$) 250 W and second (remelting) laser power ($P_{L,2}$) 187.5 W (75% of first laser scan) shows considerable improvement by lowering the amount of defect for both samples. A minimum defect of 2.02% and 1.78% is achieved for AC-380 (pre-alloyed) samples (Figure 5.33a) and AC-381 (PM-1) samples (Figure 5.33b), respectively. The maximum defect fraction is measured at $P_{L,1}$ of 200 W and $P_{L,2}$ of 100 W in AC-381 (PM-1) samples (Figure 5.33b), which is 8.28%, because of the formation of macro-sized cracks. Figure 5.33c demonstrates the amount of defect in terms of cumulative volume energy density. Increasing energy density reduces the percentage of defects (Figure 5.33c). The samples have the least defects when the volume energy density is between 120 J/mm³ and 140 J/mm³. Figure 5.33d demonstrates the sphericity of the pores with respect to cumulative volume energy density. The sphericity of the pores is increasing as increasing energy density for both AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1) samples (Figure 5.33d). The second scan laser reduces the roughness of the surface by reducing the lack of fusion porosity hence improving the relative density of the samples. Moreover, the keyhole porosity i.e the entrapment of the gas and vaporization of the particles are increasing as the energy density increases for AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1) samples.

Figure 5.33 Influence of the process parameters (a) fraction of defects for AC-380 (pre-alloyed) (b) fraction of defects for AC-381 (PM-1) (c) relationship between amount of defect and cumulative volume energy density (d) shape of the pores.

5.7.2 Heat map

Figure 5.34 shows the relationship between the temperature distributions at different heights of the samples. Initial layer shows the differences in the signal value. This is happening because of the reaction energy required to form TiB_2 . Afterwards, the pyrometer signal is identical at different heights, which means the cooling conditions are similar for both AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1) at a preheating temperature of 400 °C.

Figure 5.34 Surface temperature signal of the samples at different layer recorded by pyrometer.

5.7.3 Melt pool analysis

Figure 5.35 demonstrates the melt pool depth of the printed samples. As the first laser scan energy density is higher than the second laser scan energy density, the melt pool of both laser scans is clearly distinguishable (Figure 5.35a). Due to the substrate preheating, the sudden contraction and expansion of the melt pool has been reduced, which results in less waviness in the sample. The second laser scan remelted the surface and decreased the porosity of the samples. Also, preheating substantially reduces the viscosity of the melt pool and solidification rate, which improves the relative density of the samples by reducing overall porosity [78]. However, lack of fusion and keyhole porosities are still present in the printed samples (Figure 5.35a) and further process parameter optimization is needed. Figure 5.35b shows that increasing laser energy density increases the melt pool depth for both AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1) samples. The second laser scan energy density (Figure 5.35c) also shows similar result. The melt pool depth at higher energy density (107 J/mm^3) increases by about 24% compared to lower energy density (71 J/mm^3) for first laser scan (Figure 5.35b). Second laser scan shows similar increment in the melt pool depth.

Figure 5.35 Melt pool depth measurement at different volume energy density where (a) illustrations of melt pool and different types of porosities, (b) melt pool depth of first laser scan (c) melt pool depth of second laser scan

5.7.4 Microstructure

SEM images demonstrate the microstructure of the printed samples (Figure 5.36 and Figure 5.37). The sample AC-380 (pre-alloyed) (Figure 5.36) shows the formation of darker nano-sized particles in the grain boundaries. The size of these nano-scaled particles ranges from approximately 70 to 140 nm. As the energy density increases, the formation of the darker particles is also increases. AC-381 (PM-1) shows a similar formation of dark particles (Figure 5.37). The grain structures AC-381 (PM-1) sample (Figure 5.37) are also similar to AC-380 (pre-alloyed) samples (Figure 5.36). However, previous EDX analysis (Figure 5.24) shows these dark particles are Ti and B concentrated in the grain boundaries, which could be an indication of TiB_2 formation in the Fe-matrix.

Figure 5.36 Detailed microstructure analysis of AC-380 (pre-alloyed) as-printed sample by remelting strategy with substrate preheating.

Figure 5.37 Detailed microstructure analysis of AC-381 (PM-1) as-printed sample by remelting strategy with substrate preheating.

The grain shapes and sizes are also measured from the SEM images. The formation of dark particles is higher for higher energy density where the first laser scan energy density is 107 J/mm^3 and second laser scan energy density is 56 J/mm^3 (Figure 5.36 and Figure 5.37). The grain size is measured for this higher energy density. Figure 5.38b shows the grain size and aspect ratio for AC-380 (pre-alloyed) sample. The average grain size is about $0.89 \mu\text{m}$ for AC-380 (pre-alloyed) sample. The mean grain size of AC-381 (PM-1) sample is nearly $0.98 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 5.39b), which is slightly larger than AC-380 (pre-alloyed) sample. The mean aspect ratio is also measured for both AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1) samples from SEM images (Figure 5.36c and Figure 5.37c) which are about 1.24 and 1.27, respectively. The aspect ratio suggests the grain structure is nearly equiaxed among the printed samples with different powders.

Figure 5.38 AC-380 (pre-alloyed) at first laser scan energy density is 107 J/mm^3 and second laser scan energy density is 56 J/mm^3 where (a) SEM image (b) grain size (c) aspect ratio.

Figure 5.39 AC-381 (PM-1) at first laser scan energy density is 107 J/mm^3 and second laser scan energy density is 56 J/mm^3 where (a) SEM image (b) grain size (c) aspect ratio.

Summary: The remelting strategy with substrate preheating shows a significant decrease in the fraction of defects. Substrate preheating eliminates the cracks in the sample by lowering the thermal gradient. Increasing laser power can produce high density material. At a lower laser power, the amount of defect is still higher because of the macro-sized cracks. The heat map showed the pyrometer signal was consistent for up to 3 mm height of the sample. As the relative density of the material is highly dependent on melt pool characteristics, it is essential to choose the correct process parameter. In this study, the melt pool depth increased higher corresponding to the increase in the volume energy density. The second laser scan reduces the lack of porosity of the samples. SEM images revealed the precipitation of nano-scaled, nearly spherical darker particles along the grain boundaries. Previous EDX image (Figure 5.25) shows, these dark particles element are Ti and B. The mean grain size measurement shows similar result for both AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1) samples. Moreover, the mean aspect ratio of the grains is similar and the morphology is nearly equiaxed.

5.8 Comparison between single laser scan and remelting strategy

In this section a comparison between the sample printed by single laser scan at room temperature and the sample printed by remelting strategy with substrate preheating (400 °C) is presented and discussed.

5.8.1 Defects

Figure 5.40a shows the defects fraction for single laser scan. Higher energy density shows a significant raise in the amount of defect for AC-336 (PM-1) due to the presence of macro-sized cracks (see Figure 5.11). After applying the remelting strategy (Figure 5.40b), the fraction of defects drops from eight percent to two percent. For AC-380 (pre-alloyed) and AC-381 (PM-1), the amount of defect increased as the volume energy increased in a single laser scan. The remelting strategy reduces the porosities of the samples. The defects reduce about 8% to 2% at the energy density of 120 – 163 J/mm³ (Figure 5.40b). Further increases in energy density may decrease the defects and improves the overall quality of the sample. By varying the scanning velocity and hatch distance, the density of the material can be further improved [126].

Figure 5.40 Comparison of percentage of defects where (a) single laser scan at room temperature (b) remelting at preheating temperature of 400 °C.

5.8.2 Microstructure comparison

The microstructure of the samples printed at room temperature and substrate preheating is shown and described in sections 5.5.5 and 5.7.4. The SEM images showed nano-scaled dark particles formed in the grain boundaries (Figure 5.19 and Figure 5.37). Figure 5.41 shows, elevated fraction of dark particle formation at remelting strategy with substrate preheating compared to room temperature and single laser scan with substrate preheating. EDX images (Figure 5.25) shows the presence of Ti and B in the grain boundaries which may indicate the formation of TiB_2 in ferritic matrix. However, XRD image shows no peaks for TiB_2 (Figure 5.28). The grain size increases after using the substrate preheating (Figure 5.22b and Figure 5.39b). This is happening due to a slower solidification rate as the heat energy is stemming to the powder through the substrate plate. The grain size comparison is shown in Figure 5.41 for powder-mixture 1 (AC-336 and AC-381). Sample (AC-336) printed at room temperature has a mean grain size of about 0.71 μm . Grain size increases when the sample is printed at substrate preheating. Sample AC-381 (PM-1) printed with a remelting strategy at substrate preheating shows a maximum mean grain size of about 0.98 μm , whereas the sample printed at a single laser scan with substrate preheating has an average grain size of 0.84 μm . However, the aspect ratio remains similar.

Figure 5.41 Microstructure comparison of as printed samples where AC-336 (PM-1) printed at room temperature and AC-381 (PM-1) printed with substrate preheating.

Summary: An overall summary of the present study is listed in Table 5-9. All the samples AC-335 (pre-alloyed), AC-336 (PM-1) and AC-338 (PM-2) printed at room temperature shows a higher amount of defect at lower volume energy density (Figure 5.13d). Increasing volume energy density shows even higher fraction of defects in the samples (Figure 5.13d). Also, samples (AC-380, AC-381) printed with remelting strategy at substrate preheating shows higher amount of defect at lower energy density (Figure 5.33c). However, higher volume energy density decreases the fraction of defects (Figure 5.33c). Macro-sized and micro-sized cracks formed in all the samples printed at room temperature at lower and higher volume energy density (Figure 5.10 and Figure 5.12). Substrate preheating shows hardly any cracks at higher volume energy density, whereas lower volume energy density shows the cracks formation is occurring at the bottom or side edges of the sample (Figure 5.31 and Figure 5.32). The circularity of the pores increases as the volume energy density increase for both room temperature and remelting with substrate preheating samples (Figure 5.14d and Figure 5.33d). The melt pool depth also increases with increasing volume energy density both at RT and preheat (Figure 5.17d and Figure 5.35b and c). The grain

size increases at substrate preheating compared to RT (Figure 5.41). However, the aspect ratio is found almost similar.

Table 5-9 Effect of process parameter (energy density) of L-PBF on the key parameters/factors by single laser scan at room temperature compared to remelting strategy with substrate preheating temperature.

Parameters/Factors	Unit	Room temperature		Substrate preheat temperature			
		Single laser scan		Single laser scan		Remelting	
Volume energy density, E_v	J/mm ³	E_{vmin}	E_{vmax}	E_{vmin}	E_{vmax}	E_{vmin}	E_{vmax}
Defects	%	↑	↑↑ ¹	— ²	—	↑	↓
Cracks	%	↑	↑↑	—	—	↑	↓
Porosity shape	-	↑	↑↑	—	—	↑	↑↑
Melt pool depth	μm	↑	↑↑	↑	↑↑	↑	↑↑
Grain size	μm	—	↓	—	↑	—	↑↑
Aspect ratio	-	—	≈ ³	—	≈	—	≈

¹ ↑↑= Incremental than its predecessor.

² — = No analysis was performed

³ ≈ = Values are similar

6 Conclusion and Outlook

6.1 Conclusion

In this work, a new approach to produce in-situ Fe-TiB₂ (12 vol.%) high modulus steel via L-PBF process has been presented. The technical goal of the present study is to process metal matrix composites from powder mixtures and to get similar microstructure as pre-alloyed powder. To produce Fe-TiB₂ MMC, the powders were produced by gas atomization technology. The different powders characterization results demonstrate suitability for additive manufacturing using the L-PBF process. A comparison between pre-alloyed powder and mixing powder was also investigated. The amount of defect measured at room temperature is relatively higher. Two types of porosity such as lack of porosity and keyhole porosity are identified, which depend on the L-PBF process parameters. Higher power reduces the lack of fusion porosity. Porosities can be explained by the generation of melt pool depth. At room temperatures cracks form easily due to the large thermal gradient. Cracks originated at the bottom and side edges of the samples.

According to the hypothesis, **it is possible to make in-situ Fe-TiB₂ metal matrix composites by using elementary and binary powder mixture via L-PBF routes.** SEM investigation revealed nano-scaled dark particles are precipitated in the grain boundaries for both powder-mixture and pre-alloyed samples, which satisfies the hypothesis of this present study. The measured grain size showed similarity for both pre-alloyed and powder-mixtures. EDX investigation revealed the elements of the concentrated particle are Ti and B, which could be TiB₂. However, XRD analysis shows no peaks for TiB₂.

Afterwards, remelting strategy was adopted at room temperature to improve the quality of the samples. But the building of the samples was poor and further analysis was not carried out. Furthermore, remelting strategy with substrate preheating (400 °C) was performed. It is found that remelting strategy with substrate preheating is a promising method to decrease the amount of defect of the samples. The preheating method showed it is possible to process a sample without the formation of cracks. The remelting strategy demonstrated a reduction in the fraction of porosity. A calculated relative density of about 98% is achieved by applying this approach. Remelting strategy with substrate preheating can be a prominent approach for some applications where excellent mechanical properties are necessary. Microstructure analysis showed, the formation of TiB₂ in Fe-matrix had been affected by the L-PBF process parameters and powder-mixture. The samples showed an elevated amount

of TiB_2 after adopting remelting strategy. The samples printed with substrate preheating showed larger grain size compared to room temperature printed samples. However, the aspect ratio of the grains found similar at room temperature printed samples and remelting with substrate preheating samples.

6.2 Outlook

Based on this work, several outlooks can be derived for future research and development work regarding the processing of in-situ MMC by L-PBF technology:

- In this work, very limited L-PBF process parameters were used to process MMC. A wide range of process parameters, such as laser power, scanning velocity, and hatch distance can be tuned to process highly dense material.
- More fractional volumes of TiB_2 in Fe-matrix, such as 15% and 20% can be produced by powder-mixture and investigated and a comparison between them can be concluded.
- XRD analysis showed no peaks for TiB_2 . A TEM investigation could be performed to identify the phase.
- Mechanical performance cannot be tested due to the high amount of defect. By improving the quality of the MMC, different mechanical properties can be investigated. Additionally, the effect of micro-alloying elements on mechanical performance can be investigated.
- Melt flow is very important to processing highly dense material in L-PBF technology. The melt pool flow behavior can be studied to improve the quality of the samples. The relation between preheating temperature and solidification rate can be investigated to improve the microstructure of the samples.
- A comparison between L-PBF and other additive manufacturing technologies can be investigated.

Appendix

Table appendix

Table A-1 Process parameters for atomized powder at different gas temperatures with CCA.

Parameters (Exp. ID number)	Symbol	Unit	PA7-295	PA7-296	PA7-297	PA7-359
Alloy	-	-	Fe	FeB - 3.66 wt.%	FeTi - 16.02	FeB - 8.75 wt.%
Feed stock	-	g	3296	3000	3000	3240
Liquidus temperature	T_L	° C	1536	1175	1370	1450
Pouring temperature	-	° C	1711	1410	1520	1700
Pouring nozzle diameter	\varnothing_n	mm	3	3	3	2.5
Melting environment	-	-	Ar	Ar	Ar	Ar
Atomization gas	-	-	Ar	Ar	Ar	Ar
Atomization gas pressure	p_G	MPa	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6
Gas flow rate	\dot{M}_G	kg/h	775	775	775	775
Mean melt flow rate (feed stock mass / run time)	\dot{M}_L	kg/h	425	385	385	248
Gas-to-melt mass flow ratio	<i>GMR</i>	-	1.83	2.51	2.01	3.13

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